

RECIRCULATE

Reuse of batteries through characterisation, smart logistics, automated pack and module dismantling and repackaging and a blockchain enabled marketplace

D5.5 – 3rd Iteration Tech-Futures Analysis

WP5 – Community building, exploitation, dissemination and communication

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List of Contents	Page #
Cover page	1
Document Information, Document Revision History, Quality Control	2
Disclaimer, Copyright Message	3
List of Contents	4
List of Tables	5
List of Abbreviations	6
Executive Summary	8
1. Introduction	9
1.1 Principal objective of the RECIRCULATE project	9
1.2 Anticipated results of the RECIRCULATE project	9
1.3 Principal objective of this 3 rd Iteration RECIRCULATE T-FA	9
1.4 Positioning of the Deliverable	9
2. Methodology	10
2.1 Tech-Futures Analysis [T-FA]	10
2.2 Searching by key words, phrases and acronyms	10
2.3 Searching by Cooperative Patent Classification [CPC] codes	10
2.4 Patent database searches for this 3 rd Iteration RECIRCULATE T-FA	10
3. Results of the RECIRCULATE T-FA searches – SotA	11
3.1 SotA for the six principal RECIRCULATE technology developments	12
3.2 Overall summary of the SotA for each KER	93
4. Means of protection for the RECIRCULATE project results	94
4.1 Protection of technical intellectual property rights [IPRs]	94
4.2 Suggestions for protecting the RECIRCULATE project IPRs	94
4.3 Overall summary of suggested RECIRCULATE IPR protection strategies	95
5. Summary of the current SotA vs Freedom to Operate [FTO]	96
5.1 Patentability of the RECIRCULATE results	96
5.2 FTO with the RECIRCULATE project results	96
6. Monitoring technology developments in battery recycling	97
6.1 Setting of RECIRCULATE battery recycling alerts	97
7. Conclusions	98
ANNEX 1: Patent Status and utility models explained	99
A1.1 Patent Status	99
A1.2 Utility models	99
ANNEX 2: Disclaimer	100
END	100

List of Tables

Page #

List of start pages for Section 3.1 sections	11
Table 3.1.1 – Patents and patent applications relating to assessment protocols and equipment for SOX for packs, modules and cells	12
Table 3.1.1.1 Summary of the inventions disclosed in the publications listed in Table 3.1.1	47
Table 3.1.2 – Patents and patent applications relating to AI control processes for P2M and M2C dismantling of EV, e-bike and stationary batteries	51
Table 3.1.3 – Patents and patent applications relating to BMSs for batteries in 2nd life applications from reuse and remanufacture – update	54
Table 3.1.4 – Patents and patent applications relating to systems for battery sorting by SOX and provenance for recycling	63
Table 3.1.5 – Patents and patent applications relating to smart/safe shipping/storage solutions for 2nd life batteries	70
Table 3.1.6 – Patents and patent applications relating to blockchain-backed systems for trading of batteries and parts for 2nd life applications	85

List of Abbreviations

AEKF	Adaptive Extended Kalman Filter
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Autoregression
ANN	Artificial Neural Network
BGIP	Background Intellectual Property = IP brought to the project by the partners
BMS	Battery Management System
BPNN	Back-Propagation Neural Network
CAN	Controller Area Network
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
CBAM	Convolutional Block Attention Module
CCV	Closed Circuit Voltage
CPC	Cooperative Patent Classification
DCIR	Direct Current Internal Resistance
DI/DO	Data In/Data Out
DOD	Depth/Degree of Discharge
D&S	Dismantling & Sorting
E3D-LSTM	Eidetic 3D-Long Short-Term Memory
ECM	Equivalent Circuit Model
EIS	Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy/Spectroscopy
EKF	Extended Kalman Filter
EoL	End of Life
FCM	Fuzzy C-Means
FGIP	Foreground Intellectual Property = IP associated with the project results
GA	Genetic Algorithm
GA-LSTM-NN	Genetic Algorithm-Long Short-Term Memory-Neural Network
GCN	Graph Convolutional Network
GNN	Graph Neural Network
HF	Heat Flow
INN	Informer-based Neural Network
IWOA	Improved Whale Algorithm
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment/Analysis
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
LEL	Lower Explosive Limit
LOL	Limiting Oxygen Level
LSTM-NN	Long Short-Term Memory-Neural Network
M2C	Module-to-Cell

ML	Machine Learning
MLP-NN	Multi-Level Perceptron-Neural Network
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
NN	Neural Network
NSSR	Nonlinear State Space Reconstruction
OCV	Open Circuit Voltage
OPEX	Operating Expenditure
P2M	Pack-to-Module
PCC	Pearson Correlation Coefficient
PINN	Physics-Informed Neural Network
PSO	Particle Swarm Optimization
RF	Random Forest
S-LCA	Social-LCA
SOC	State of Charge
SOH	State of Health
SOP	State of Power
SOR	State of Reuse
SOR	State of Risk
SOS	State of Safety
SOS	State of Short
SR-UKF	Square Root-Unscented Kalman Filter
SSA	Sparrow Search Algorithm
TCN	Temporal Convolutional Network
TEA	Techno-Economic Assessment
T-FA	Tech-Futures Analysis
TR	Thermal Runaway
UH	Enthalpy potential

Executive Summary

Principal objective of the RECIRCULATE project

Reuse of batteries through characterisation, smart logistics, automated pack and module dismantling and repackaging and a blockchain enabled marketplace – RECIRCULATE

The main aim of the RECIRCULATE project is defined in this extract from the Grant Agreement:

'RECIRCULATE addresses the needs of the European recycling sector by overcoming current challenges relating to automated dismantling and sorting; safe logistics; fast, cost-effective and reliable SOH and SOS characterization. Combining these advances with a blockchain-based platform, that will combine the data collected during dismantling and recycling and the battery provenance, will enable a unique battery passport and virtual marketplace for e-mobility, consumer and stationary battery ESSs. This approach will enable the RECIRCULATE consortium to create a cascade approach that will enable increased end-of-life battery repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycling.'

Purpose of this 3rd Iteration RECIRCULATE Tech-Futures Analysis [T-FA]

To assess the potential of the proposed outputs of the RECIRCULATE project [FGIP] for patent-protection and exploitation IIL has used its IP associate, **EUREXPLOIT LTD**, to carry out this review into patenting activity in battery recycling, the **3rd Iteration T-FA**, as part of Deliverable **D5.5** to:

- ✓ update the State of the Art [SotA] in each RECIRCULATE project technology development area
- ✓ identify any new competing technologies that have been published since the **2nd Iteration T-FA** report was completed in September 2024
- ✓ identify no-go areas where project technology developments might lead to third-party patent infringements
- ✓ confirm continued Freedom to Operate [FTO] with the planned technology developments.

The analysis was carried out as described in **Section 2** below. Briefly, key words, phrases and acronyms were used along with Cooperative Patent Classification codes [CPC codes] in **T-FA** activities to identify the most recent and relevant granted patents and patent applications. The results of those activities are presented and analysed in **Section 3** and reviewed in **Section 4** and **Section 5** thereafter.

Overall conclusions on the SotA for RECIRCULATE technology developments

The results of the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA** confirm the conclusions stated in the report on the **2nd Iteration T-FA**:

- ✓ No patent application or granted patent discovered in the **T-FA** searches discloses technology that appears to duplicate **all** or **even several** of the features of the proposed RECIRCULATE system
- ✓ None of the patents or applications discovered appears to infringe the partners' IPRs in their own technology patents.

Overall conclusion regarding FTO with the RECIRCULATE project results

From the observations made above, it may be inferred that the project partners can seek patent protection for their developments in end-of-life battery repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycling. However, alternative means are available for the protection of the technical developments made in the RECIRCULATE project and their associated intellectual property rights [IPRs], these are discussed in **Section 4** of this report.

1. Introduction

1.1 Principal objective of the RECIRCULATE project

Reuse of batteries through characterisation, smart logistics, automated pack and module dismantling and repackaging and a blockchain enabled marketplace – RECIRCULATE

The main aim of the RECIRCULATE project is defined in this extract from the Grant Agreement:

'RECIRCULATE addresses the needs of the European recycling sector by overcoming current challenges relating to automated dismantling and sorting; safe logistics; fast, cost-effective and reliable SOH and SOS characterization. Combining these advances with a blockchain-based platform, that will combine the data collected during dismantling and recycling and the battery provenance, will enable a unique battery passport and virtual marketplace for e-mobility, consumer and stationary battery ESSs. This approach will enable the RECIRCULATE consortium to create a cascade approach that will enable increased end-of-life battery repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycling.'

1.2 Anticipated results of the RECIRCULATE project

The main technological developments anticipated in the RECIRCULATE project were summarised in the proposal as these Key Exploitable Results [KERs]:

KER1 – Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

KER2 – Validated AI-backed control process for automated pack to module and module to cell dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

KER3 – BMS for monitoring and control of batteries in second-life applications from reuse and remanufacture

KER4 – Process definition for faster and more accurate sorting by SOX and battery provenance (including the cathode and anode materials) for recycling

KER5 – Smart/safe shipping/storage solution for second-life batteries

KER6 – Blockchain-backed marketplace prototype (TRL8) for trusted trading of batteries and related components for reuse, remanufacture or recycling

1.3 Purpose of this 3rd Iteration RECIRCULATE Tech-Futures Analysis [T-FA]

To assess the potential of the proposed outputs of the RECIRCULATE project [FGIP] for patent-protection and exploitation IIL has used its IP associate, **EUREXPLOIT LTD**, to carry out this review into patenting activity in battery recycling, the **3rd Iteration T-FA**, as part of Deliverable **D5.5** to:

- ✓ update the State of the Art [SotA] in each RECIRCULATE project technology development area
- ✓ identify any new competing technologies that have been published since the **2nd Iteration T-FA** report was completed in September 2024
- ✓ identify no-go areas where project technology developments might lead to third-party patent infringements
- ✓ confirm continued Freedom to Operate [FTO] with the planned technology developments.

The analysis was carried out as described in **Section 2** below. Briefly, key words, phrases and acronyms were used along with Cooperative Patent Classification codes [CPC codes] in **T-FA** activities to identify the most recent and relevant granted patents and patent applications. The results of those activities are presented and analysed in **Section 3** and summarised in **Section 4** thereafter.

1.4 Positioning of the Deliverable

The Deliverable **D5.5** brings together three iterations of **T-FA**. One last iteration will be undertaken, close to the project's end. This final analysis will enable an assessment of the value of the partners' foreground intellectual property [FGIP] and how that may be exploited using the RAPID strategy outlined in the RECIRCULATE Grant Agreement.

2. Methodology

2.1 Tech-Futures Analysis [T-FA]

This report is based on the use of **Tech-Futures Analysis [T-FA]**. A **T-FA** includes, *inter alia*, a review of the current State of the Art (SotA) in each relevant technology sector, set alongside prior art and FTO analyses. Altogether RECIRCULATE partner **III** will carry out three iterations of **T-FA** for the RECIRCULATE project – together forming Deliverable **D5.5**. To identify key patents relevant to development of the RECIRCULATE end-of-life battery repair, reuse, remanufacture and recycling system, along with current Freedom To Operate [FTO] in the relevant technology sectors, we have enhanced the usual keyword searches by using a citation analysis technology that is proprietary to Ampercite Pty Ltd and Griffith Hack, both of Melbourne, Australia. Together they developed powerful string algorithms for the analysis of patent citations which enable filtering, grouping, ranking and charting of cited patents and applications – Amberscope [AS]. In addition, they developed AI algorithms that enable an analysis of the similarities (and hence the differences) between the inventions disclosed in patents.

2.2 Searching by key words, phrases and acronyms

Searching the various patent databases, such as Google Patents, Espacenet and the USPTO database, using key words, phrases and acronyms alone can lead to lack of accuracy. It is easy to miss patents and applications because of misspellings, alternative spellings, specific usage of words and phrases unknown to the researcher, etc. However, such searches can be useful if they identify key patents which can in turn be used to identify Cooperative Patent Classification codes [CPC codes] applicable to the technology being researched.

For the purposes of this **3rd Iteration T-FA**, Google Patent and Espacenet databases were interrogated using key words, phrases and acronyms including, but not limited to: *'pack, battery, module, cell, electric vehicle battery, second life battery, end of life, life cycle, dismantling, thermal runaway, limiting oxygen level, lower explosive limit, smart, artificial intelligence, AI, machine learning. ML, robot, transport, storage, recyc*, repurpos*, reus*, life cycle assessment/analysis, LCA, life cycle costing, LCC'*.

*N.B. The * operator picks out all words with the same trunk e.g., recycle, recycled, recycles, recycling, recyclable*

2.3 Searching by Cooperative Patent Classification [CPC] codes

The Cooperative Patent Classification [CPC] system enables all filed patents and applications in e.g. the Espacenet and USPTO databases to be searched logically and rapidly. To the right is an example of a CPC code:

B	29	C	39	/023
Section	Class	Sub-class	Group	Sub-Group

Following our initial searches using a range of key words and phrases, the key CPC codes that define the anticipated RECIRCULATE inventions were identified. These are exemplified by but not limited to:

H01M 2010/4278 – Systems for data transfer from batteries

Y02W 30/00 – Technologies for solid waste management

Y02W 30/50 – Reuse, recycling or recovery technologies

2.4 Patent database searches for this **3rd Iteration RECIRCULATE T-FA**

The chosen key CPC codes, words and phrases were then entered into the patent database search engines, e.g. Espacenet Advanced Search engine, to identify the most recent and relevant published patents and patent applications. The search results were then assessed for their relevance to this study's objectives by:

- ✓ checking the status of each patent application at the relevant intellectual property office;
- ✓ checking the Background to each invention;
- ✓ examining the Description and Claims in the published documents for relevance;
- ✓ checking the Assignees/Applicants vs their record in this technology sector.

3. Results of the RECIRCULATE T-FA searches – SotA

3.1 SotA for the six principal RECIRCULATE technology developments

The main intention of the **3rd Iteration T-FA** searches presented here is to update the State of the Art in the six principal technological developments to be made in the RECIRCULATE project.

Date range for the searches – This **3rd Iteration T-FA** report includes mostly publications made since the SotA was reviewed for the **2nd Iteration T-FA**, i.e. since September 2024. From **Section 1.2** above, those technical developments can be summarised as:

KER1 – Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

KER2 – Validated AI-backed control process for automated pack to module and module to cell dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

KER3 – BMS for monitoring and control of batteries in second-life applications from reuse and remanufacture

KER4 – Process definition for faster and more accurate sorting by SoX and battery provenance (including the cathode and anode materials) for recycling

KER5 – Smart/safe shipping/storage solution for second-life batteries

KER6 – Blockchain-backed marketplace prototype (TRL8) for trusted trading of batteries and related components for reuse, remanufacture or recycling

The specifications above were used in determining which patents and patent applications from the hundreds discovered in the **T-FA** searches were most relevant to updating the SotA. Those publications are presented in **Table 3.1.1** through **Table 3.1.6** in the following **Sections 3.1.1** through **3.1.6**. The number of the start page in this document of each of those sections is provided in the following table:

Section	Section title	Starts
3.1.1	Assessment protocols and equipment for SOX for packs, modules and cells	p.12
3.1.2	AI control processes for P2M and M2C dismantling of EV, e-bike and stationary batteries	p.51
3.1.3	BMSs for batteries in 2 nd life applications from reuse and remanufacture	p.54
3.1.4	Systems for battery sorting by SOX and provenance for recycling	p.63
3.1.5	Smart/safe shipping/storage solutions for 2 nd life batteries	p.70
3.1.6	Blockchain-backed systems for trading of batteries and parts for 2 nd life applications	p.85

Each table commences with an update of the **Status** of each patent application, if any, that was included in the **2nd Iteration T-FA** report and was still under examination at the time that report was completed. Each publication listed in the tables of that report has an associated Report Ref. #, **RECIRC2-XX**, which is used again in this document.

Regarding the new patent applications identified in the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA** report, each has an associated Report Ref. #, **RECIRC3-XX**, which is used throughout this document.

The reference numbers can be found in **Column 1** of the lists in each table. The following details of each patent or patent application are also provided in each table:

Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
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The results are presented in each table in order of **Priority date** from the earliest to the most recent.

3.1.1 Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.1 – Patents and patent applications relating to assessment protocols and equipment for SOX for packs, modules and cells			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-04	US20230417838 (A1) Jun 28th 2022 EXICOM TELE SYSTEMS LTD [IN] Dec 28th 2023	<p>SYSTEM FOR ESTIMATION OF STATE OF HEALTH OF BATTERY PACK AND METHOD THEREOF</p> <p>A method and system for estimation of State of Health [SOH] of a battery pack is provided.</p> <p>The method includes determining a first SOH utilizing a set of operational parameters and a first set of stress parameters and a second SOH based on a determined discharge capacity.</p> <p>Utilizing the first and the second SOH, determine a second set of stress parameters of the battery pack.</p> <p>The method includes determining a third SOH of the battery pack based on at least one selected second set of stress parameters and the set of operational parameters and determining a deviation parameter based on the first and the third SOH.</p> <p>Thereafter, the method includes transmitting an ideal SOH signal to one of a server and a user device in response to the determined deviation parameter being greater than a pre-defined threshold.</p> <p>Updated status Non-Final Rejection posted – Sep 15th 2025</p>	<p>FIG. 3 is an interaction of an at least one processor with the plurality of functionality modules of the system of FIG. 2 to estimate the SOH of the battery pack, according to one or more embodiments of the present invention.</p> <p>The transceiver 205 of the system may be implemented as a device adapted to aid in one of receiving and transmitting at least one of, but not limited to, the set of operational parameters and the estimated SOH to the at least one processor 210.</p>

<p>RECIRC2-05</p>	<p>KR20240061221 (A) Oct 31st 2022 WONKWANG ELEC CO [KR] May 8th 2024</p>	<p>APPARATUS FOR ESTIMATING SOH OF BATTERY PACK</p> <p>The present invention relates to a device for estimating the lifespan of a secondary battery pack.</p> <p>More specifically, it estimates the lifespan (SOH, State Of Health) of the battery pack by learning the voltage trend during charging and discharging of the battery pack based on artificial intelligence.</p> <p>Updated status No information since Oct 31st 2022 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-06</p>	<p>CN116520149 (A) Jan 31st 2023 JIANGSU WEIHENG INTELLIGENT TECH CO LTD [CN] Aug 1st 2023</p>	<p>REAL-TIME STATE MONITORING METHOD FOR DISTRIBUTED ENERGY STORAGE BATTERY</p> <p>The real-time state monitoring method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, constructing an alliance block chain;</p> <p>S2, calculating and storing the state of the battery through a BMS (Battery Management System);</p> <p>S3, the BMS communicates with the Internet of Things equipment, and sends the state information obtained in the S2 to the Internet of Things equipment;</p> <p>S4, uploading the information on the Internet of Things equipment to a block chain, and storing the information in a shared database of an operation and maintenance provider;</p> <p>S5, the alliance block chain provides a public key and a private key for the node user, and the node user can access the shared database of the block chain through the public key to obtain the state information of the battery.</p> <p>According to the monitoring method, programs are accessed and transacted with other node users through a private key, monitoring parameters of the energy storage battery comprise a state of charge (SOC), a state of health (SOH), an electric quantity state (SOP), an energy state (SOE), a temperature state (SOT) and a safety state (SOS), and meanwhile, the timeliness and the safety of data are improved through linkage of the Internet of Things and a block chain technology.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected twice – amended document still under examination</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-08</p>	<p>CN116609689 (A) Mar 27th 2023 STATE GRID ZHEJIANG ELECTRIC POWER CO LTD HUZHOU POWER SUPPLY CO [CN] Aug 18th 2023</p>	<p>RETIRED LITHIUM BATTERY COMPLEMENTARY ENERGY RAPID DETECTION METHOD BASED ON ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE</p> <p>The method aims to solve the problems of low accuracy and high application cost of a current decommissioned lithium battery performance detection method. It comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, building an artificial intelligence-based neural network prediction model;</p> <p>S2, detecting single lithium batteries with different old and new degrees to obtain sample data;</p> <p>S3, generating a training sample set, training the neural network prediction model, and correcting a training sample according to a training output result; and</p> <p>S4, inputting charge and discharge data of the retired lithium battery into the trained neural network prediction model to obtain a final detection result.</p> <p>According to the method, the retired lithium battery is detected by establishing the neural network prediction model based on artificial intelligence, the detection accuracy is improved by correcting and adjusting the neural network prediction model, the application cost is low, and the method has wide applicability.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 1st Office Action Dec 11th 2025</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-09</p>	<p>CN116540106 (A) May 30th 2023 YANCHENG INST TECH [CN] Aug 4th 2023</p>	<p>PARALLEL BATTERY SYSTEM SOC ESTIMATION METHOD BASED ON FUZZY COMPENSATOR</p> <p>The method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>building a battery system model parameter according to a known battery monomer model parameter, then detecting the current of each branch, carrying out the subtraction between the current of each branch and 1/N of a battery system current measurement value I_b, and obtaining each difference value ΔI_i and the difference value change rate $\Delta I_i/dt$ as the input of the fuzzy compensator;</p> <p>the fuzzy compensator is composed of N fuzzy sub-controllers, a compensation value ΔSOC_b is obtained through the fuzzy compensator, and then the compensation value ΔSOC_b is superposed with an SOC initial value SOC_0 to obtain a new SOC_i;</p> <p>the difference value ΔU_{if} and the difference value change rate $\Delta U_{if}/dt$ of the difference value ΔU_{if} are obtained and serve as input of a fuzzy controller, a feedback value SOC_r is obtained through the fuzzy controller, the feedback value SOC_r is subtracted from the SOC_i, and the SOC of the battery system is obtained;</p> <p>the SOC serves as input, battery system model parameters are obtained through a battery system model parameter module in combination with battery monomer model parameters, and then a battery system equivalent model is updated.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>Rejected at 1st Office Action Sep 11th 2025</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-12</p>	<p>CN117074960 (A) Aug 21st 2023 CHANGCHUN INST TECH JILIN COMMUNICATIONS POLYTECHNIC [CN] Nov 17th 2023</p>	<p>POWER LITHIUM BATTERY PACK SOH PREDICTION METHOD AND SYSTEM</p> <p>The method comprises the following steps: firstly, collecting cycle data, including current, voltage, temperature, internal resistance, coulombic efficiency, cycle index and other parameters, of a power lithium battery pack, and performing preprocessing operation to obtain standard cycle data; carrying out traditional prediction through an attenuation empirical model and carrying out regression prediction through an MLP network to obtain a first initial SOH predicted value and a second initial SOH predicted value; and comparing the second initial SOH predicted value with an actual SOH value, and performing weight parameter correction by using a T-S fuzzy controller to obtain a second SOH predicted value. And finally, performing model fusion on the first SOH predicted value and the second SOH predicted value to obtain a final SOH predicted value so as to realize accurate prediction of the health state of the power lithium battery pack.</p> <p>The power lithium battery pack SOH prediction method and system provided by the invention have wide application prospects in the field of battery management, and can provide powerful support for monitoring and maintenance of the battery pack.</p> <p>Updated status No information since Aug 21st 2023 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-13</p>	<p>CN117330959 (A) Sep 28th 2023 SHANGHAI MAKESENS ENERGY STORAGE TECH CO LTD [CN] Jan 2nd 2024</p>	<p>JOINT CALIBRATION METHOD, SYSTEM AND DEVICE FOR SOC AND SOH OF BATTERY AND MEDIUM</p> <p>The joint calibration method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>charging a plurality of batteries in a battery pack with a preset charging current until the first fully charged battery appears in the battery pack;</p> <p>the remaining batteries which are not fully charged in the battery pack are charged through a charging equalizer until all the batteries are fully charged;</p> <p>calibrating the SOC of all batteries in the battery pack as 100%;</p> <p>a plurality of continuous pulse currents are synchronously sent to all the batteries through the charging equalization instrument, and a voltage signal of each battery is recorded;</p> <p>calculating the direct-current internal resistance of each battery according to the pulse current and the voltage signal;</p> <p>and determining the SOH of the battery pack according to the DC internal resistance and a preset internal resistance range.</p> <p>Accurate calibration of the SOC and the SOH is achieved, the calibration principle is simple, operation is convenient, the calibration accuracy is improved, the service life of the battery pack can be effectively prolonged, and the performance of the battery pack is improved.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Jan 2nd 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>FIG. 5 is a schematic diagram of the structure of an electronic device provided in Embodiment 3 of the present invention.</p> <p>The electronic device 30 may be in the form of a general-purpose computing device, for example, it may be a server device. It includes at least one processor 31 mentioned above, at least one memory 32 mentioned above, and a bus 33 connecting different system components (including the memory 32 and the processor 31. The bus 33 includes a data bus, an address bus, and a control bus. The memory 32 may include a volatile memory, such as a random access memory (RAM) 321 and/or a cache memory 322, and may further include a read-only memory (ROM) 323. The memory 32 may also include a program/utility 325 having a set (at least one) of program modules 324, such program modules 324 including but not limited to: an operating system, one or more application programs, other program modules, and program data, each of which or some combination may include an implementation of a network. The electronic device 30 may also communicate with one or more external devices 34 (e.g., buttons, pointing devices, etc.). Such communication may occur via an input/output (I/O) interface 35. The device 30 can also communicate with one or more networks, such as the Internet, via a network adapter 36.</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-14</p>	<p>CN117352884 (A) Sep 28th 2023 DONGFENG COMMERCIAL VEHICLE CO LTD [CN] Jan 5th 2024</p>	<p>POWER BATTERY SYSTEM AND BATTERY STATE ESTIMATION METHOD THEREOF</p> <p>The invention relates to the technical field of electric vehicles, in particular to a power battery system and a battery state estimation method thereof.</p> <p>Step 1, in the first charging working condition, charging all the battery branches until all the battery branches are fully charged.</p> <p>Step 2, entering a discharge working condition, selecting a group of battery branches as a group to be measured, enabling the group to be measured to discharge in an accelerated manner, and enabling other battery branches to discharge normally until the power battery system ends the discharge working condition or the battery branches of the group to be measured are used up.</p> <p>Step 3, when the power battery system is in the charging working condition again, if the electric quantity of the to-be-measured battery pack branch is used up in the last discharging working condition, executing the step 4;</p> <p>Step 4, calculating the SOH of the branch according to the Qx of the branch of the battery pack to be measured; and replacing a group of battery branches as a group to be measured, and continuing to execute the subsequent operation from the step 2 until all the battery branches are estimated.</p> <p>Result: the SOC and SOH states of each single battery in each branch of the battery system can be accurately measured.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Sep 28th 2023 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>FIG1 is a schematic diagram of system connection of the present invention.</p> <p>1-power battery system; 10-battery branch; 101-battery cell; 2-positive voltage regulating contactor; 3-positive bus contactor; 4-negative bus contactor; 5-branch current sensor; 6-battery management system; 7-DC-DC converter</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-15</p>	<p>CN117388738 (A) Sep 28th 2023 HUIZHOU EVE ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Jan 12th 2024</p>	<p>BATTERY THERMAL RUNAWAY TEST METHOD AND DEVICE AND ELECTRIC VEHICLE SYSTEM</p> <p>The battery thermal runaway test method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>placing a target battery in a reaction environment to be continuously heated, and a first target parameter is continuously obtained in the heating process;</p> <p>calculating a second target parameter according to the first target parameter;</p> <p>and comparing the second target parameter with a preset condition of thermal runaway, and if the second target parameter meets the preset condition, judging that the state of the target battery is a thermal runaway state.</p> <p>When thermal runaway occurs in different SOC modes in a non-adiabatic environment, thermal runaway triggering conditions of the battery are detected, a whole-system early warning temperature is provided for thermal runaway of the battery in different SOC modes, early warning parameters are provided for practical application of the battery, and reference is provided for model selection of electric vehicle system parts.</p> <p>Parts such as a single battery explosion-proof valve, a battery pack explosion-proof valve and a smoke sensor are adopted, the test cost is low, and the thermal runaway test of large-capacity and large-size single batteries can be compatible.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Jan 12th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>FIG. 5 is a schematic structural diagram of a battery thermal runaway testing device provided in an embodiment of the present application.</p> <p>10 - explosion-proof box; 20 - target battery; 701 - temperature acquisition equipment; 702 - voltage acquisition equipment; 703 - air pressure acquisition equipment; 80 - pressure relief valve; 801 - vacuum pump; 90 - air collection bag; 100 - DC power supply; 110 - air source.</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-18</p>	<p>CN117471326 (A) Nov 9th 2023 HARBIN INST TECHNOLOGY WEIHAI [CN] Jan 30th 2024</p>	<p>LITHIUM ION BATTERY PACK DYNAMIC INCONSISTENCY AND HEALTH STATE EVALUATION METHOD</p> <p>The method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>processing acquired abnormal data, and segmenting continuously acquired data into segments to obtain an average voltage curve;</p> <p>after obtaining the segmented monomer (=cell) voltage data and average voltage data, evaluating the similarity between the monomer voltage and the average voltage by using DTW (Dynamic Time Warning) to obtain the similarity between each monomer and the average voltage of the segment;</p> <p>after obtaining the similarity, estimating probability density distribution from the similarity of each monomer of each fragment, and performing probability density estimation by using a kernel function to obtain a probability density function;</p> <p>and after a probability density function is obtained, an inconsistency index is solved for each fragment, data fitting is carried out after abnormal values are removed by applying DBSCAN, and a final SOH change curve is obtained.</p> <p>The method is small in external interference, low in sampling precision requirement, high in robustness to abnormal data and better in adaptability to real vehicle data and cloud data.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Jan 30th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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RECIRC2-19

CN117572248 (A)

Nov 20th 2023

UNIV CENTRAL
SOUTH [CN]

Feb 20th 2024

FUSION METHOD FOR SOH ESTIMATION AND ENERGY BALANCE OF SERIES LITHIUM ION BATTERIES

The method comprises the following steps:

S1, determining a balance variable, and designing an energy balance strategy which can be used for a series lithium ion battery pack;

S2, designing an equalizing current expected value prediction method based on feed-forward compensation, and solving by using an intelligent optimization algorithm (firefly algorithm);

and

S3, researching a relational expression between the equalizing current and the SOH, screening out a voltage interval with the most stable charge, and carrying out rapid and high-precision individual SOH estimation.

In order to solve the problem of optimization of battery monomer (=cell) estimation in a series battery pack and the problem of comprehensive consideration of an energy balance strategy, average balance current in a certain voltage range is adopted, factors such as calculation burden, inconsistency and charge sensitivity are considered, and capacity correlation among battery monomers is derived by utilizing an energy transfer relation, so that the energy balance strategy is comprehensively considered.

Result: completing SOH estimation of all the battery monomers in all the groups.

Updated status

No information since Nov 20th 2023 – fate currently unknown

FIG. 1 is a schematic diagram of a topological structure of a battery equalizer circuit.

<p>RECIRC2-20</p>	<p>CN117849623 (A) Dec 4th 2023 UNIV EAST CHINA SCIENCE & TECH [CN] SHANGHAI INST SPACE POWER SOURCES [CN] SHANGHAI AEROSPACE POWER TECHNOLOGY CO LTD [CN] Apr 9th 2024</p>	<p>METHOD FOR ESTIMATING STATE OF CHARGE OF BATTERY PACK BASED ON DIFFERENCE MODEL</p> <p>The invention provides a difference model-based battery pack state-of-charge estimation method, which comprises the following steps of:</p> <p>based on a mixed pulse power test experiment, performing state-of-charge-open-circuit voltage measurement on single batteries under the same process, and fitting a state-of-charge-open-circuit voltage function;</p> <p>acquiring current and voltage data of the battery pack to be detected, wherein the current and voltage data comprise external current and external voltage of each battery monomer;</p> <p>selecting an equivalent circuit model as a difference model, and establishing a state-space equation; according to the state-space equation and the current and voltage data, identifying model parameters through a forgetting factor-based least square method to obtain a deviation value of the open-circuit voltage of each single battery;</p> <p>the average open-circuit voltage is determined through the state of charge of the battery pack, and the state of charge of each single battery is solved by combining the deviation value of the open-circuit voltage.</p> <p>According to the estimation method, the SOC performance of the battery pack can be estimated on line, the required calculation amount is reduced, and the estimation method is still suitable for some working conditions with large sampling intervals.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Apr 9th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-21</p>	<p>CN117743970 (A) Dec 6th 2023 UNIV CHONGQING [CN] Mar 22nd 2024</p>	<p>RETIRED BATTERY THERMAL RUNAWAY EARLY WARNING METHOD BASED ON AI DATA RECONSTRUCTION AND INTEGER OPTIMIZATION</p> <p>The invention relates to a decommissioned battery thermal runaway early warning method based on AI data reconstruction and integer optimization, and belongs to the field of decommissioned battery safety early warning.</p> <p>According to the method, the reconstruction error of the time sequence data of the decommissioned batteries is calculated through variational neural network data reconstruction so as to define the difference degree between the decommissioned batteries, and the reconstruction error basic model is constructed by using the idea that the normal data reconstruction error is small and the abnormal data reconstruction error is large.</p> <p>And then an electrochemical decommissioned battery thermal runaway early warning frame based on integer optimization is proposed to quantify the decommissioned battery thermal runaway probability and enhance the model stability, and the integrated model is further optimized, so that the integrated model achieves higher precision on the premise of smaller basic model combination scale.</p> <p>According to the method, the accuracy and the stability of thermal runaway early warning of the retired battery are improved, the integrated model is optimized, the false alarm rate is reduced, the service life of the battery is prolonged, and the reutilization of the retired battery is promoted.</p> <p>Updated status No information since Dec 6th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-22</p>	<p>CN117962613 (A) Jan 26th 2024 CHONGQING CHANGAN AUTOMOBILE CO LTD [CN] May 3rd 2024</p>	<p>ACTIVE ANTI-EXPLOSION CONTROL METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR THERMAL RUNAWAY OF POWER BATTERY, VEHICLE AND MEDIUM</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>obtaining the SOC state of a battery and the concentration of at least one preset combustible gas in a battery pack, and checking a concentration relation table of different gases in different SOC states according to the SOC state of the battery and the concentration of the preset combustible gas;</p> <p>obtaining a ratio estimation value of each gas in the battery pack in the current SOC state; calculating a lower limit estimation value of detonation limit in the battery pack according to each gas proportion estimation value and the SOC state of the battery;</p> <p>and comparing the deflagration limit lower limit estimation value in the current SOC state with the deflagration limit lower limit calibration value in the corresponding SOC state, judging the deflagration risk level in the battery pack, and controlling the opening degree of an anti-explosion ventilation valve of the battery pack according to the deflagration risk level.</p> <p>According to the invention, real-time estimation of the proportion of the combustible gas in the battery pack can be realized, and active control of the concentration of the combustible gas in the battery pack is realized through hierarchical control of the opening degree of the explosion-proof ventilation valve.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since May 6th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>FIG. 4 is a schematic diagram of the arrangement position of the CO sensor in an embodiment of the present application.</p> <p>1-CO sensor 1, 2-explosion-proof ventilation valve, 3-battery pack</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-23</p>	<p>CN117930063 (A) Jan 29th 2024 UNIV BEIJING TECHNOLOGY {CN} STATE GRID CHONGQING ELECTRIC POWER CO [CN] Apr 26th 2024</p>	<p>METHOD FOR PREDICTING STATE OF HEALTH OF RETIRED BATTERY BASED ON ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY AND DRT</p> <p>The invention relates to a method for predicting the state of health of a decommissioned battery based on electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) and distribution of relaxation times (DRT), and belongs to the field of battery prediction.</p> <p>The method comprises the following steps of EIS experiment and data extraction, analysis of EIS data by a DRT technology, establishment of a Genetic Algorithm-Long Short Term Memory-Neural Network (GA-LSTM-NN) and SOH prediction.</p> <p>According to the method for processing the relaxation time of the lithium ion battery on the alternating-current impedance, the EIS comprises a lot of information of the battery, and the accuracy of a test result is high.</p> <p>Genetic algorithm optimization is added into the LSTM neural network, so that parameters in the LSTM can be ensured to be better, and the SOH prediction effect is effectively improved.</p> <p>According to the method, the input set and the output set are constructed on the basis of establishing complete battery test data, so that the SOH is predicted by the LSTM neural network, the accuracy is high, and the practicability is high.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since Jan 29th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-24</p>	<p>CN118011208 (A) Mar 1st 2024 UNIV WUHAN TECH CHINA ELECTRIC POWER RES INST CO LTD [CN] May 10th 2024</p>	<p>LITHIUM ION BATTERY MONOMER INTERNAL STATE MONITORING SYSTEM</p> <p>The invention comprises an optical fiber sensing network, an optical fiber grating demodulator and a data processing unit.</p> <p>A main body of the optical fiber sensing network is arranged in the lithium ion battery, and the optical fiber sensing network is used for acquiring a temperature signal and a strain signal in the lithium ion battery.</p> <p>The fiber Bragg grating demodulator is in communication connection with the optical fiber sensing network and is used for receiving the temperature signal and the strain signal and sending the demodulated temperature signal and strain signal to the data processing unit.</p> <p>The data processing unit is in communication connection with the fiber Bragg grating demodulator and is used for determining the SOC value of the battery based on the demodulated temperature signal and strain signal.</p> <p>According to the invention, accurate monitoring of the battery management system is realized.</p> <p>Updated status</p> <p>No information since May 10th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	<p>FIG. 1 is a schematic structural diagram of an embodiment of a lithium-ion battery cell internal state monitoring system provided by the present invention. The fiber optic sensing network 10 includes a single optical fiber 11, a plurality of fiber grating temperature sensors 12, a plurality of fiber grating strain sensors 13 and a substrate material 14, wherein the plurality of fiber grating temperature sensors 12 and the plurality of fiber grating strain sensors 13 are all attached to the single optical fiber 11, and the substrate material 14 is coated on the plurality of fiber grating temperature sensors 12 and the plurality of fiber grating strain sensors 13 and fixedly connected to the single optical fiber 11.</p>
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RECIRC3 publications

<p>RECIRC3-01</p>	<p>KR20240146386 (A) Mar 29th 2023 GYEONGBUK INSTITUTE OF IT CONVERGE INDUSTRY TECH [KR] Oct 8th 2024</p>	<p>CAN ELECTRIC CAN DATA-BASED BATTERY LIFE PREDICTION SYSTEM USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE</p> <p>A battery life prediction system based on electric vehicle CAN data using artificial intelligence [AI] according to the present invention includes:</p> <p>a vehicle information collection device to collect data output from a battery management system via an on-board diagnostic device [OBD] and transmit the data using a wireless network;</p> <p>a CAN data storage server configured to store and manage data collected from the OBD; and</p> <p>an AI prediction server for predicting the battery life using a modeled result using AI based on the data collected from the CAN data storage server.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as KR102885215 (B1) – Nov 11th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of deep/machine learning algorithms based on battery current, voltage, temperature, charge and power data to predict life of an EV battery.</p>	<p>FIG. 2, the vehicle information collection device (100) collects CAN data using an OBD device from data output from a battery management system (BMS) (10) that manages the battery.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-02</p>	<p>JP2025064945 (A) Oct 5th 2023 HITACHI LTD [JP] Apr 17th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY PACK PROCESSING METHOD, NON-TRANSITORY COMPUTER READABLE MEDIUM, AND BATTERY PACK PROCESSING APPARATUS</p> <p>PROBLEM: There is no implementation that infers cell-level or module-level SOH from pack-level SOH.</p> <p>SOLUTION: A battery pack processing method includes the steps of: processing a battery pack to determine a structure of the battery pack and a state of health (SOH) of the battery pack; and determining appropriate recycle, retrofit, repurpose, or reuse instructions according to estimated distribution of a viable cell count and/or a module count based on the state of health of the battery pack.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted in Japan as JP7791268 (B2) – Dec 23rd 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of an algorithm to infer cell-level or module-level SOH from pack-level SOH to determine if batteries should be used or diverted to second-life uses. One of only a few found that specifically discloses assessment of SOH for reuse, etc., see e.g., (RECIRC3-11) below.</p>	<p>FIG. 10, the battery packs may be transported (e.g., via a conveyor belt, via a cart, etc.) under a scanner that scans information about the battery pack. The scanner can scan the battery pack (e.g., barcode, RFID tag, etc.) to identify manufacturer and OEM information, and from there, reference a database to obtain the battery pack structure, including cell and module information and cell or module prior SOH probability distribution information, which can then be provided to a server, such as a computing device.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-03</p>	<p>AU2024200894 (A1) Jan 22nd 2024 HONG KONG METROPOLITAN UNIV [CN] Aug 7th 2025</p>	<p>METHOD FOR ESTIMATION OF STATE OF CHARGE AND STATE OF HEALTH IN A LITHIUM-ION BATTERY PACK, AND SYSTEM THEREOF</p> <p>A machine learning method of estimating State of Charge (SOC) and State of Health (SOH) of a battery pack, the method comprising:</p> <p>collecting a plurality of time-series data related to operational parameters of a battery pack;</p> <p>processing the collected time-series data utilizing a Nonlinear State Space Reconstruction (NSSR) algorithm to reconstruct a first phase state space reconstruction;</p> <p>training a first LSTM-NN model using the first phase state space reconstruction for predicting SOH of said battery pack;</p> <p>feeding the time-series data to the first LSTM-NN to predict an estimated SOH value of the battery pack;</p> <p>processing the time-series data utilizing said NSSR algorithm to reconstruct a second phase state space reconstruction;</p> <p>training a second LSTM neural network model using the second phase state space reconstruction, taking into account the estimated SOH value, for predicting SOC of the battery pack, and feeding the time-series data and the estimated SOH value of the battery pack to the second LSTM neural network to obtain an estimated SOC value.</p> <p>A system configured to perform the above method is also disclosed.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as AU2024200894 (B2) – Aug 28th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of two LSTM-NNs for simultaneous estimation/prediction of SOC and SOH of a battery pack.</p>	<p>FIG. 4 shows a structure of joint SOC and SOH estimation based only on LSTM-NNs.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-05</p>	<p>WO2025197736 (A1) Mar 22nd 2024 PANASONIC IP MAN CO LTD [JP] Sep 25th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY ANALYSIS SYSTEM, BATTERY ANALYSIS METHOD, BATTERY ANALYSIS PROGRAM, BATTERY PACK, AND RECORDING MEDIUM RECORDING BATTERY ANALYSIS PROGRAM</p> <p>A data acquisition unit (111) acquires battery data including the voltage and current of a secondary battery included in a battery pack. An SOH estimation unit (113) estimates the SOH by using a two-point open circuit voltage (OCV) method. An SOH progress curve generation unit (115) uses a calculated plurality of SOH sample data to perform curve regression and generate an SOH progress curve for the secondary battery. A period confirmation unit (112) confirms the sampling period of the battery data. The SOH progress curve generation unit (115) increases a weighting to the extent of the SOH calculated on the basis of the battery data in a section in which the sampling period is short.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Written Opinion of the International Search Authority*</p> <p>Novelty: Claims 1-9: YES</p> <p>Inventive Step: Claims 1-9: YES</p> <p>Industrial Applicability: Claims 1-9: YES</p> <p>*See ANNEX 1 of this document for more information on this</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of a mobile phone App for the real-time, non-invasive assessment of SOC and SOH of a battery pack on an e-bicycle.</p>	<p>FIG. 1 is a diagram illustrating a battery analysis system 10 according to an embodiment.</p> <p>A battery analysis system 10 according to the embodiment is a system that analyzes a battery pack 30 mounted on a battery-mounted device (an electric bicycle 1 in this embodiment). The battery pack 30 and a mobile terminal device 20 (e.g. a smartphone) carried by a user are connected via short-range wireless communication, e.g. via Bluetooth. The mobile terminal device 20 can access the network 2 to which the battery analysis system 10 is connected via a mobile phone network (4G/5G) or Wi-Fi.</p>
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RECIRC3-06

CN120831594 (A)

Apr 16th 2024

ROBERT BOSCH CO
LTD [DE]

Oct 24th 2025

METHOD FOR IMPROVING ACCURACY OF DETERMINATION OF STATE OF CHARGE

A method for improving the accuracy of a determination of a state of charge [SOC] of a battery pack, where the method comprises at least the steps of:

performing a repeated plurality of loads on the battery pack by charging and discharging at least one battery of the battery pack;

detecting an open-circuit voltage remaining on the battery at a plurality of set charge state points to generate a charge open-circuit voltage curve, a discharge open-circuit voltage curve, and an average open-circuit voltage [OCV] curve for the battery pack; **generating an average open-circuit voltage curve;**

determining a charging state lag function; determining a lag factor K, or determining an expanded lag factor;

the average OCV curve is adapted through a first method and a second method, and charging state lag is calculated; generating a separate curve for the SOC hysteresis value;

the individual curves are applied to determine a state-of-health [SOH] value and an end-of-life {EoL} value for the battery pack.

Status

Under examination

Comment – Discloses estimation of SOH and EoL values for a battery pack using SOC hysteresis curves.

FIG. 2 shows multiple SOC hysteresis curves in the SOC hysteresis chart 200, which represent the SOC values of a battery pack under different SOC values 206, states of discharge 208, and SOHs 210.

<p>RECIRC3-07</p>	<p>CN120840404 (A) Apr 26th 2024 CHINA RESOURCES MICROELECTRONICS CHONGQING CO LTD [CN] Oct 28th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY HEAT ENERGY EARLY WARNING CONTROL METHOD AND SYSTEM AND NEW ENERGY VEHICLE</p> <p>The method comprises the steps that</p> <p>(1) a feedback current matrix of a battery module is set;</p> <p>(2) controlling charging and discharging of the battery module based on the feedback current matrix, and performing temperature control on the battery pack based on the environment temperature; (</p> <p>3) in the process of the step 2), training and updating the SOC curve local model, fitting the SOC curve, judging that the SOC curve is normal when the SOC curve converges, judging that the SOC curve is abnormal when the SOC curve diverges, and sending out a first early warning signal;</p> <p>meanwhile, monitoring the temperature rise of the battery module, judging that the battery module is normal when the temperature rise speed is less than a third preset value, and judging that the battery module is abnormal when the temperature rise speed is greater than or equal to the third preset value;</p> <p>when the first early warning signal and the second early warning signal are both effective, charging and discharging are stopped, and fault early warning is sent out; and</p> <p>(4) in the process of the step (2), if the working state exceeds the safety protection range, fault early warning is given out, and fire extinguishing and explosion prevention measures are started.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comments – Discloses an explosion-safe management system based on SOC</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-08</p>	<p>CN118688683 (A) May 20th 2024 UNIV NORTH CHINA ELECTRIC POWER [CN] Sep 24th 2024</p>	<p>BATTERY SAFETY STATE QUANTIFICATION METHOD AND SYSTEM CONSIDERING BATTERY LIFE</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>arranging a plurality of sensors for monitoring the state parameters of the battery in real time in an energy storage system, and storing the collected state parameter data in a database;</p> <p>constructing a battery state of safety [SOS] quantization function, wherein the battery SOS quantization function and the charge state have the same numerical range; and quantifying the battery SOS of the energy storage system by using the battery SOS quantification function.</p> <p>Compared with the prior art, according to the technical scheme, the quantitative expression mode of the SOS of the battery is scientifically constructed, multiple battery parameters are comprehensively considered, comprehensive and accurate evaluation of the SOS of the battery of the energy storage system is achieved, potential safety hazards can be found in time, accidents are avoided, and the method has good application prospects.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of multiple sensors in determining the real time SOS of a battery pack. Application of the derived safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>Three flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-09</p>	<p>CN118859007 (A) Jun 24th 2024 HEFEI GUOXUAN HIGH TECH POWER ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Oct 29th 2024</p>	<p>BATTERY PACK INTERNAL GAS CONTENT MONITORING METHOD AND APPLICATION THEREOF</p> <p>The detection method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, aging a battery to enable the battery to enter a specific SOH state;</p> <p>S2, putting the aged battery into a closed gas tank, and opening an anti-explosion valve of the battery in a triggering manner; and</p> <p>S3, performing chromatographic analysis on the gas in the gas tank, and establishing a database of the content of the gas in the battery.</p> <p>According to the method, a battery pack thermal runaway gas content database is established by monitoring the variety and content change trend of gas released by the battery in the process from different use working conditions to valve opening, and thermal runaway can be warned to a certain extent by subsequently monitoring the real-time change of gas in the battery pack.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses means for identifying and detecting the concentration of gases that might lead to thermal runaway of battery packs. A database is developed that allows prediction of runaway events and that informs a triggering of an explosion-proof valve. To prevent inflammable gas build up. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is a schematic diagram of the gas tank part of the present invention;</p> <p>In the diagram: 1. Gas tank; 2. Gas chromatograph; 3. Piping; 4. Valve; 5. Return gas pipe; 6. Collection tube; 7. Air bag.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-10</p>	<p>CN118859014 (A) Jul 23rd 2024 MONTA VISTA ENERGY TECH CORPORATION ANHUI [CN] Oct 29th 2024</p>	<p>LITHIUM METAL BATTERY CYCLE LIFE PREDICTION METHOD AND APPLICATION</p> <p>The prediction method comprises the following steps: carrying out cyclic charge and discharge test on a contrast lithium metal battery, recording median voltage and internal resistance at the starting time and the ending time, and calculating an ending parameter; testing the lithium metal battery to be tested, continuously recording the median voltage and the internal resistance, and performing curve fitting to obtain a fitting formula; and the cycle life is predicted.</p> <p>The method is based on only carrying out charge-discharge cycle, recording the change of the discharge direct-current internal resistance and the median voltage and establishing the model without destructive disassembly; and is particularly suitable for realizing the qualitative and quantitative prediction of the cycle life of the lithium metal battery after the lithium metal battery is modularized.</p> <p>The data prediction method uses data fitting on the basis of a small amount of measured data, and compared with pure theoretical calculation and an empirical model, the prediction method has higher universality and higher accuracy.</p> <p>Status No information since Jul 23rd 2024 – fate currently unknown</p> <p>Comment – Discloses non-destructive characterization of the SOH of LIBs after they are modularized.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-11</p>	<p>CN119471444 (A) Nov 4th 2024 HUBEI TECHPOW ELECTRIC CO LTD [CN] Feb 18th 2025</p>	<p>METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR RAPIDLY EVALUATING HEALTH DEGREE OF RETIRED BATTERY</p> <p>According to the method, the historical operation data of the decommissioned battery are obtained and input into the back-propagation neural network [BPNN] algorithm, so that the historical estimated value of the current capacity of the decommissioned battery is obtained, meanwhile, the existing estimated value of the current capacity of the decommissioned battery is obtained by combining the characteristic frequency impedance, and the external parameter change of the battery in the actual working condition is comprehensively considered.</p> <p>According to the method and the system, the historical operation data and the characteristic frequency impedance of the battery are subjected to characteristic screening according to the change of the internal structure and the material in the aging process of the battery, and the historical estimated value and the existing estimated value are fused to obtain the SOH of the decommissioned battery, so that the subsequent management of a new battery pack is facilitated, and the efficiency of the decommissioned lithium battery is improved.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – One of only a few patent publications found that specifically discloses assessment of SOH of retired batteries for reuse, etc., see (RECIRC3-02) above for another example. External, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy [EIS] and a BPNN are used in the characterisation process.</p>	<p>A flow chart of the method is provided but annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-12</p>	<p>CN119864528 (A) Jan 16th 2025 BAISHITONG ZHEJIANG SAFETY TECH CO LTD [CN] Apr 22nd 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY RISK EARLY WARNING MANAGEMENT AND CONTROL SYSTEM AND METHOD</p> <p>The invention provides a battery risk early warning management and control system that comprises a weak grating temperature sensor, a weak grating vibration sensor, an optical fiber grating hydrogen concentration sensor, an optical fiber signal demodulator, a gas filling module, a gas pressure detection module, a risk early warning module, a remote terminal and a management and control module. The weak grating temperature and vibration sensor and the fiber Bragg grating hydrogen concentration sensor are used for sensing the temperature, the vibration condition and the released hydrogen concentration generated due to the abnormal safety and health state of the battery in the battery pack.</p> <p>The risk early warning module carries out early warning reminding according to risk data, and the gas filling module is used for filling nitrogen into the battery pack. And when the gas pressure detection module detects that the air pressure in the battery pack exceeds the standard, the lead seal automatically falls off.</p> <p>According to the system, the inert gas is filled into the battery pack, and the battery temperature, the vibration condition and the hydrogen concentration are monitored in real time by virtue of the sensor to perform risk management and control, so that the battery is effectively prevented from fire explosion.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN119864528 (B) – Jan 30th 2026</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of nitrogen in suppressing thermal runaway of batteries in a pack. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is an internal structural diagram of the battery risk warning and control system according to an embodiment of the present invention;</p> <p>Reference numerals: 1. Weak grating temperature detection module; 11. Weak grating temperature sensor; 2. Weak grating vibration detection module; 21. Weak grating vibration sensor; 3. Fiber Bragg grating gas concentration detection module; 31. Fiber Bragg grating gas concentration sensor; 4. Fiber optic signal demodulator; 41. Photodetector; 42. Data analysis unit; 5. Gas filling module; 6. Gas pressure detection module; 7. Early warning module; 8. Remote terminal; 9. Control module; 10. Fiber optic cable.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-13</p>	<p>CN120233236 (A) Apr 15th 2025 HANGZHOU LIDE COMMUNICATION CO LTD [CN] Jul 1st 2025</p>	<p>SOC (STATE OF CHARGE) STATE ESTIMATION SYSTEM AND ESTIMATION METHOD USED IN BMS (BATTERY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM)</p> <p>The SOC state estimation system comprises a current signal conditioning circuit, a voltage detection circuit and an SOC estimation module.</p> <p>The input end of the current signal conditioning circuit is connected with the positive electrode of the battery pack;</p> <p>the input end of the voltage detection circuit is connected with the positive and negative electrodes of the battery pack respectively;</p> <p>the voltage detection circuit is used for obtaining an open-circuit voltage OCV of the battery pack and is connected to a data sampling port of the SOC estimation module;</p> <p>the current signal conditioning circuit is used for detecting the current of the battery pack and is connected to a data sampling port of the SOC estimation module;</p> <p>on one hand, the SOC estimation module calculates an initial value SOC₀ when the battery pack works according to a pre-stored battery model and an open-circuit voltage OCV, and on the other hand, the SOC estimation module calculates an SOC value of the battery at any moment according to current and an ampere-hour integral method.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120233236 (B) – Oct 21st 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses realization of the SOC of the battery by combining OCV and ampere-hour integral methods.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-14</p>	<p>CN120122019 (A) May 12th 2025 CHINA COAL RES INST [CN] Jun 10th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY PACK HEALTH STATE PREDICTION METHOD, DEVICE, EQUIPMENT, MEDIUM AND PROGRAM PRODUCT</p> <p>The invention comprises the following steps:</p> <p>acquiring battery pack temperature data, battery pack current data and battery pack voltage data of at least two battery packs in a preset time period;</p> <p>calculating the temperature difference of the battery packs at each time point based on the battery pack temperature data, and calculating the temperature similarity between the battery packs according to the temperature difference;</p> <p>calculating current similarity between the battery packs based on the frequency domain representation of the battery pack current data;</p> <p>calculating a covariance matrix of voltage change based on the voltage data of the battery packs, and calculating the voltage similarity between the battery packs according to the covariance matrix;</p> <p>constructing a temperature adjacency diagram, a current adjacency diagram and a voltage adjacency diagram based on the temperature similarity, the current similarity and the voltage similarity; and</p> <p>predicting the health state of the battery pack based on the temperature adjacency diagram, the current adjacency diagram and the voltage adjacency diagram through a preset SOH prediction model.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120122019 (B) – Jul 25th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses means for assessing the SOH of a whole battery pack.</p>	<p>Four flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-15</p>	<p>CN120142987 (A) May 13th 2025 BBK TEST SYSTEMS CO LTD [CN] Jun 13th 2025</p>	<p>NEW ENERGY AUTOMOBILE POWER BATTERY HEALTH STATE DETECTION METHOD BASED ON MIGRATION FROM SINGLE BODY TO BATTERY PACK</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>collecting the voltage data of a single battery in a cycle charging stage, and constructing a pre-trained single battery SOH evaluation model;</p> <p>extracting a charging stage voltage curve of the battery pack;</p> <p>performing deep feature migration on the charging stage voltage curve of the battery pack to obtain target battery pack data;</p> <p>based on the target battery pack data, retraining the single battery SOH evaluation model to obtain a battery pack SOH evaluation model; and</p> <p>performing new energy automobile power battery health state detection by using the battery pack evaluation model.</p> <p>According to the invention, the SOH evaluation method for migration from the single battery to the vehicle battery pack is designed, an evaluation model is optimized by using small-scale sample data, and rapid evaluation of the SOH of the battery pack through a small-scale sample data set is realized by selecting a proper model main network and an innovative deep neuron feature optimization method.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120142987 (B) – Aug 29th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses that the SOH of the pack is derived from individual cells rather than the reverse as disclosed in RECIRC3-02 above, using a long short-term memory neural network [LSTM-NN] model and a three-layer fully connected neural network [NN] model.</p>	<p>Three flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-16</p>	<p>CN120507659 (A) May 27th 2025 HUIZHOU SIHAI JIANCHENG IND CO LTD [CN] SHENZHEN XINGXIA AUTOMOTIVE TECH CO LTD [CN] Aug 19th 2025</p>	<p>ELECTRIC VEHICLE BATTERY HEALTH ASSESSMENT METHOD AND SYSTEM BASED ON MULTI-SOURCE DATA FUSION</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>collecting a Nyquist impedance curve, terminal voltage relaxation time sequence data and equalization current time sequence data based on a constant current stage cut-off event of a battery pack of an electric vehicle;</p> <p>extracting an impedance form embedding vector corresponding to the Nyquist impedance curve based on an auto-encoder;</p> <p>performing wavelet packet decomposition on the terminal voltage relaxation time sequence data to obtain a corresponding multi-scale voltage relaxation energy feature vector;</p> <p>calculating a dynamic equalization imbalance index based on the terminal voltage relaxation time sequence data and the equalization current time sequence data; and</p> <p>inputting the impedance form embedded vector, the multi-scale voltage relaxation energy feature vector and the dynamic equilibrium imbalance index into a battery SOH prediction model to output an SOH estimated value of the battery pack.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120507659 (B) – Nov 11th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of multi-data fusion and joint modeling of the coupling characteristics of the multi-physical processes of batteries in estimating/predicting the SOH of battery packs. Application to EoL battery packs prior to reuse is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>Four flow charts and one figure are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-17</p>	<p>CN120334756 (A) Jun 20th 2025 WHEATFIELD ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Jul 18th 2025</p>	<p>SOH ESTIMATION METHOD OF BATTERY PACK</p> <p>The invention provides an SOH (state of health) estimation method for a battery pack, which comprises the following steps of:</p> <p>S1, acquiring a capacity label value required for estimating the SOH of the battery pack based on historical actual operation data of the battery pack, and constructing a sliding window input data matrix related to the SOH;</p> <p>S2, inputting a data matrix based on a sliding window, and automatically extracting a health feature map related to the aging of the battery pack through a neural network; and</p> <p>S3, based on the extracted health feature map, modeling is carried out on battery attenuation dynamics through a physics-informed neural network [PINN], and estimation of the SOH of the battery pack is realized.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120334756 (B) – Sep 30th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of a global feature extraction network, a graph feature extraction network, a multilayer fully connected neural network, and a PINN for estimation of battery pack SOH.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-18</p>	<p>CN120831578 (A) Jul 23rd 2025 CHINA MERCHANTS INDUSTRIAL INTELLIGENT TECH JIANGSU CO LTD [CN] Oct 24th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY SOC PREDICTION ALGORITHM BASED ON E3D-LSTM AND BATTERY CELL POSITION STRUCTURE CHARACTERISTICS</p> <p>The method comprises the steps that</p> <p>Establishing a three-dimensional matrix according to the position structure and battery parameters of batteries in a battery pack to serve as input data;</p> <p>performing standardization processing on the input data, and constructing a training set, a verification set and a test set by using the processed input data;</p> <p>constructing a battery SOC prediction model based on an eidetic 3D-LSTM [E3D-LSTM] algorithm, and determining basic structure parameters of the model; before</p> <p>training, verifying and testing the battery SOC prediction model based on the E3D-LSTM by using the training set, the verification set and the test set..</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Rejected at 1st Office Action for lack of clarity – Jan 9th 2026</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the first application of an E3D-LSTM algorithm to SOC prediction found in the searches for any iteration of RECIRCULATE T-FA.</p>	<p>One flow chart and four figures provided but each is annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-19</p>	<p>CN120629978 (A) Jul 25th 2025 UNIV ZHEJIANG TECHNOLOGY RUIPU LANJUN ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Sep 12th 2025</p>	<p>LITHIUM ION BATTERY SAFETY STATE ESTIMATION METHOD BASED ON WORKING CONDITION FRAGMENT CHARACTERISTICS AND UNSUPERVISED CLUSTERING</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>achieving the segmentation of different working condition data based on K-means based on an MIT-Stanford mixed working condition cycle data set;</p> <p>for the segmentation data, segment safety features and global safety features of the constant current charging stage, the constant voltage charging stage and the constant current discharging stage are extracted respectively;</p> <p>performing normalization, direction unification, dimension reduction and correlation screening processing on a data set formed by feature extraction in sequence, and combining to generate a plurality of feature data sets;</p> <p>aiming at a plurality of security feature sets, adopting a particle swarm optimization [PSO] algorithm to optimize fuzzy C-means [FCM] clustering center selection, introducing GG distance measurement to replace Euclidean distance, and establishing an SOS estimation method based on PSO-fuzzy clustering;</p> <p>independently clustering each feature set, giving a 0/1 score according to different clustering center results; and</p> <p>finally aggregating a good reputation rate as an SOS estimated value.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of a a particle swarm optimization [PSO] algorithm to optimize fuzzy C-means [FCM] clustering center selection for estimation of battery SOS.</p>	<p>FIG. 6 Based on the PCC analysis results between the filtered features, three features in each group (with $PCC \leq 0.7$) were selected and combined. Features were allowed to be reused to cover complete information, and finally 107 feature groups were generated to provide input for PSO-GG clustering.</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER1 – Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

The RECIRCULATE system for assessment of used battery packs, modules and cells is characterised by **(1)** a controller area network [CAN] connecting **(2)** the BMS from which historic/present **(3)** non-invasive/non-destructive test data and/or **(4)** invasive/destructive test data from the used battery module can be **(5)** *rapidly* transmitted to **(6)** a battery interface unit (BIU), along with **(7)** stimulus-response data, for ingestion and processing by **(8)** an (AI/ML) algorithm/calculation to deliver **(9)** SOX outputs – SOC/SOH/SOS. The characteristics of the systems disclosed in the publications listed in **Table 3.1.1** above, including those carried over from the **2nd Iteration T-FA** and those found during the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA**, are compared to those of the RECIRCULATE system, **(1)** through **(10)**, in the following table:

RECIRCULATE system →	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RECIRC2-XX Ref # ↓	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
RECIRC2-04	-	-	✓	-	(✓)	✓	✓	-	✓
RECIRC2-05	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	DL-NN	✓
RECIRC2-06	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-08	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	ANN	✓
RECIRC2-09	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	Fuzzy Comp ^r	✓
RECIRC2-12	-	-	✓	-	-	(✓)	-	MLP-NN	✓
RECIRC2-13	-	-	✓	-	-	✓	✓	-	✓
RECIRC2-14	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-15	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-18	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-19	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-20	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC2-21	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	ANN	✓
RECIRC2-22	-	-	✓	-	-	(✓)	-	✓	-

RECIRC2-23	-	-	✓	-	-	-	-	GA-LSTM-NN	✓
RECIRC2-24	-	-	-	(✓)	-	(✓)	-	-	✓
KEY	✓ = Specifically disclosed in the patent or application - = Not specifically disclosed (✓) = Partly disclosed or implied								

RECIRC3-XX Ref # ↓	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
RECIRC3-01	✓	✓	-	-	-	(✓)	-	✓	✓
RECIRC3-02	(✓)	✓	-	-	-	(✓)	-	✓	✓
RECIRC3-03	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	NSSR LSTM-NN	✓
RECIRC3-04	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	KALMAN FILTER	✓
RECIRC3-05	(✓)	✓	-	-	-	(✓)	-	NN	✓
RECIRC3-06	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	✓	✓
RECIRC3-07	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	✓
RECIRC3-08	-	(✓)	✓	-	-	(✓)	-	✓	✓
RECIRC3-09	-	(✓)	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓
RECIRC3-10	-	✓	✓	-	-	-	-	✓	(✓)
RECIRC3-11	-	✓	✓	-	-	✓	-	DBSCAN	✓
RECIRC3-12	-	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	-	(✓)
RECIRC3-13	-	✓	✓	-	(✓)	✓	✓	OCV	✓
RECIRC3-14	-	✓	✓	-	✓	✓	-	Multi-GCN	✓

								Temporal STM Transformer	
RECIRC3-15	-	✓	✓	-	(✓)	-	-	LSTM-NN 3-layer fully connected NN	✓
RECIRC3-16	✓	(✓)	✓	-	-	-	-	LSTM-NN TCN Transformer	✓
RECIRC3-17	-	✓	(✓)	-	-	-	-	LSTM-NN GCN, CNN PINN, CBAM	✓
RECIRC3-18	-	(✓)	(✓)	-	-	-	-	E3D-LSTM	✓
RECIRC3-19	-	(✓)	✓	-	-	-	-	FCM clustering PSO	✓
KEY	✓ = Specifically disclosed in the patent or application - = Not specifically disclosed (✓) = Partly disclosed or implied								

Table 3.1.1.1 Summary of the inventions disclosed in the publications listed in Table 3.1.1

Notes to the table

1. Many hundreds of patent applications disclosing measurement of SOXs were found during the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA**. For example, over 200 more applications disclosing measurement of the SOC of a battery pack have been published since searches on this topic were undertaken until September 2024 for the **2nd Iteration T-FA** report. Those listed in **Table 3.1.1** were chosen as the more relevant of the publications discovered.
2. It is clear from **Table 3.1.1.1** that each of the publications listed in **Table 3.1.1** discloses one or more inventions that show some degree of overlap with the battery assessment technology developments that the partners plan to make/have made during the RECIRCULATE project. However, none discloses all or even most of them.
3. It appears that the speed by which examiners in the Chinese patent office have granted patent applications related to novel SOX measurement technologies has accelerated rapidly over the past two years. Prior to 2024, examination of such applications might take two to three years whereas some applications made in 2025, like **RECIRC3-14** through **RECIRC3-17**, have gone from filing to grant in six months or less. This would seem to indicate the desire of the Chinese government to maintain the country's leading edge in development of EV-related technologies, including advances in recycling of EV batteries.

4. Although this author of this report is not an expert in different types of neural networks [NNs] and other forms of algorithms applied to determining the SOX characteristics of retired EV batteries, it seems to us that there is an increasing complexity to the number and type of those that are being used for SOX measurement, whether alone or in combination, in recent patent applications – see list at characteristic **(8)** in the table.

Overall summary – The same conclusion can be reached here as in the report for the **2nd Iteration T-FA** namely that : “From the analysis of publications disclosing means for measuring battery SOH, SOC, SOS, etc., it is obvious that this is a saturated patent landscape and that the beneficiaries will have to create a system that is highly novel and deeply non-obvious should they wish to patent their own approach(es) to such measurements. In addition, they will have to take all the teachings of the listed publications, and more, into account when submitting any patent application of their own.” It may also be concluded that Chinese enterprises continue to be the main competitors for the RECIRCULATE partners in this technology sphere.

3.1.2 AI control processes for automated P2M and M2C dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.2 – Patents and patent applications relating to AI control processes for P2M and M2C dismantling of EV, e-bike and stationary batteries			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-27	CN117117374 (A) Aug 30th 2023 JIANGXI ISUZU MOTORS CO LTD [CN] Nov 24th 2023	POWER BATTERY PACK RECOVERY METHOD AND SYSTEM The method comprises the steps that: the power battery pack is input into a preset disassembling system, and the power battery pack is disassembled into a plurality of corresponding battery components through the preset disassembling system; obtaining factory battery parameters corresponding to the power battery pack from a preset battery database and constructing a corresponding battery detection model based on a preset neural network according to the factory parameters; actual battery parameters corresponding to the battery components are detected, the attenuation rate of each battery component is calculated according to the actual battery parameters through a battery detection model, and the battery components are classified and recycled according to the attenuation rates. Updated status No information since Aug 30 th 2023 – fate currently unknown	No particularly informative figure available

RECIRC3 publications

<p>RECIRC3-20</p>	<p>CN119251305 (A) Sep 23rd 2024 UNIV SOUTHEAST [CN] Jan 3rd 2025</p>	<p>POSITION AND POSTURE ESTIMATION METHOD FOR BATTERY REPLACEMENT ROBOT BASED ON POINT CLOUD COMPONENT SEGMENTATION AND REGISTRATION</p> <p>The method comprises the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, placing a 3D visual sensor below an electric vehicle chassis to shoot a to-be-replaced battery pack, and obtaining an RGB color image and a depth image containing a battery pack locking and unlocking device in a scene; 2, acquiring a locking and unlocking instance segmentation mask of the acquired color image by using a convolutional neural network [CNN], and projecting the instance into a locking and unlocking point cloud in combination with the acquired depth map and camera internal reference; 3, statistical filtering and voxel filtering are carried out on the locking and unlocking point cloud, point cloud noisy points are removed, down-sampling is carried out, and the point cloud data quality is improved; 4, segmenting a point cloud of the locking and unlocking lock through a Point Net point cloud segmentation network; and 5, solving the important part of the locking and unlocking lock point cloud by using a principal component analysis method, calculating the FPFH feature of the important part, searching the corresponding relationship between the scene lock point cloud and the template lock point cloud through an RANSAC method to complete coarse registration, and finally, optimizing the registration result by using ICP to obtain the estimated pose of locking and unlocking. <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN119251305 (B) – Oct 17th 2025</p>	<p>A flow cart and two figures are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER2 – Validated AI-backed control process for automated pack to module and module to cell dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

Notes

1. No patent publication was found that discloses an AI-backed process for automated P2M or M2C dismantling of automotive EV, e-bike or stationary batteries.
2. **RECIRC3-20** is included here as the most relevant publication found because it discloses use of a CNN in assisting a robot to disconnect a to-be-replaced battery pack from underneath an EV.

Overall summary – No patent or patent application was found that discloses application of AI to the process of disassembling retired/waste EV battery packs or modules, whether by robot or not.

3.1.3 Battery management systems for batteries in 2nd life applications from reuse and remanufacture

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.3 – Patents and patent applications relating to BMSs for batteries in 2 nd life applications from reuse and remanufacture – update			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-28	WO2024167781 (A1) Feb 6 th 2023 SAMSTAR RESOURCES LLC [US] Aug 15 th 2024	<p>BATTERY PACK INCLUDING BATTERY MODULES AND METHODS OF MAKING THE BATTERY PACK AND REPURPOSING THE BATTERY MODULES</p> <p>A battery pack includes a plurality of interlocked battery modules, a plurality of battery cells located in the battery module housings, and a battery management system (BMS) unit electrically coupled to the plurality of battery cells.</p> <p>Extract – One or more of the battery modules may be joined together to form a battery pack at either higher voltages in a series electrical connection or higher capacities in a parallel electrical connection.</p> <p>The battery modules may be joined in series or parallel connection to form the battery pack which may provide environmental protection and structural integrity.</p> <p>The architecture of the battery module may make it simple to validate the performance of each battery module in the battery pack. This simplicity may allow the battery architecture to greatly simplify the process of repurposing the battery module at the end of its first life.</p> <p>Updated status No information since Dec 8th 2024 – fate currently unknown</p>	

RECIRC3 publications

RECIRC3-21

GB2623643 (A)
 Oct 21st 2022
 CIRRUS LOGIC INT
 SEMICONDUCTOR
 LTD [GB]
 Apr 24th 2024

A SYSTEM FOR PERFORMING A MEASUREMENT ON A COMPONENT

A system 300, for performing a measurement on a component 120, comprises an integrated circuit (IC) 150 with an analogue to digital converter (ADC) 130 and processing circuitry 140. Difference circuitry 320 generates a compensated measurement voltage by subtracting a compensation voltage received from an external voltage source 310 from a measurement voltage output by the component in response to a stimulus signal received by the component. The stimulus signal is an AC signal of variable frequency produced by a signal generator 110.

The component may be a battery or electrochemical cell and the measurements may be electrochemical impedance spectrum [EIS] measurements.

Alternatively, the difference circuit may be a digital subtractor and both the output of the component and the external voltage source may be digitized by ADCs before the difference circuit. **The compensation voltage may be a DC voltage offset to remove the DC component of the EI spectrum.**

Status

Granted as **GB2623643 (B)** – Jan 8th 2025

Comment – Discloses a system that includes an integrated circuit for use in performing EIS measurements on, *inter alia*, batteries. Use on parallel collation of EI spectra from multiple batteries is not specifically disclosed.

RECIRC3-22

KR20230026615 (A)
 Aug 18th 2021
 KOREA ADVANCED
 INST SCI & TECH [KR]
 Feb 27th 2023

ARCHITECTURE FOR MEASUREMENT SYSTEM DESIGNED FOR MASSIVE IMPEDANCE EXTRACTION OF BATTERY SYSTEMS

The architecture comprises an EIS module (100) in which an EIS IC (110)* is provided in a parallel structure so that individual signal generation and signal collection functions can be performed individually for individual impedance extraction of each battery cell, and an interface (200) provided to connect the EIS module (100) to a central data bus of a separately provided data processing device (11).

Accordingly, **the impedance of a battery can be extracted in a large-scale parallel manner**, and thus it is possible to improve the reliability and stability of the battery.

***Each EIS IC (110) can be implemented as a monolithic integrated circuit capable of performing signal generation, signal amplification, signal collection, signal processing, and reporting functions.**

Status

Granted as **KR102579043 (B1)** – Sep 15th 2023

Comment – The first found to disclose the use of EIS-ICs in large-scale parallel impedance extraction from battery modules/packs.

FIG. 5 is a drawing illustrating an example of an architecture for an impedance measurement system illustrated in FIG. 3 implemented to enable expansion of an EIS module.

<p>RECIRC3-23</p>	<p>CN119029989 (A) Oct 11th 2024 SHENZHEN JIECHENG NICKEL COBALT NEW ENERGY TECH CO LTD [CN] Nov 26th 2024</p>	<p>ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEM BASED ON RETIRED BATTERY</p> <p>The battery management unit is used for obtaining operation information of the decommissioned battery module and transmitting the operation information to a control input end of a control unit, and a switching control circuit is provided with an input end and an output end. The input end of the switching control circuit is connected to the charging output port of the battery management unit, the output end of the switching control circuit is connected to the input end of the DC-DC conversion circuit, the output end of the DC-DC conversion circuit is connected to the output port, the output port supplies power to direct current electric equipment, the control unit is provided with a switching control output end and a switching control output end, and the switching control output end is connected with the switching control output end.</p> <p>The switching control output end of the control unit is connected to the control input end of the switching control circuit, and the switching control output end of the control unit is connected to the control input end of the DC-DC conversion circuit.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a BMS for retired batteries being used in a second life as energy storage units.</p>	<p>No particular informative figure provided</p>
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RECIRC3-24

CN120217013 (A)

Mar 24th 2025

UNIV JINAN [CN]

Jun 27th 2025

MATCHING DECISION-MAKING METHOD AND SYSTEM FOR STORAGE AND RECOMBINATION LINKAGE MANAGEMENT AND CONTROL OF RETIRED POWER BATTERY

The method comprises the steps:

detecting at least one piece of recombination decision-making information to be executed from first recombination matching decision-making information after recombination correction information is received, and enabling one piece of recombination decision-making information to be associated with one first recombination order;

combining a dynamic recombination order corresponding to the recombination correction information and all the first recombination orders into a second recombination order, and performing coding and population initialization on all the second recombination orders according to preset mixed integer programming to generate a plurality of candidate coding individuals;

based on a preset catastrophe adaptive genetic algorithm [GA], mixed integer programming and the fitness corresponding to the candidate coding individuals participating in each iteration, performing iteration of genetic evolution operation and population catastrophe operation on the plurality of corresponding candidate coding individuals until a plurality of intention coding individuals are generated; and

obtaining a decision result including the target coding individual.

Status

Granted as **CN120217013 (B)** – Oct 3rd 2025

Comment – Discloses a matching decision-making method and system for the coordinated management and control of the storage and reorganization of retired power batteries.

FIG. 3 is a schematic diagram of chromosomes according to an embodiment of this application.

<p>RECIRC3-25</p>	<p>CN120389139 (A) May 6th 2025 JIANGSU HUAYOU ENERGY TECH CO LTD [CN] Jul 29th 2025</p>	<p>UNIVERSAL ECHELON UTILIZATION METHOD FOR BATTERY MODULES</p> <p>The invention relates to the technical field of battery management, and discloses a battery module general echelon utilization method, which comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, carrying out performance detection on a retired battery module;</p> <p>S2, connecting the battery module to the echelon utilization system through the lossless access device;</p> <p>S3, integrating a module-level battery management module in each battery module;</p> <p>S4, arranging a direct current-direct current conversion module in each module;</p> <p>S5, a system-level battery management module is arranged on the battery system level; and</p> <p>S6, when the module has a fault, isolating the fault module through the system-level battery management module.</p> <p>According to the invention, through the standardized design of the sampling interface and the power interface, and in combination with a lossless access technology, universal access of battery modules with different models, specifications and performances is realized.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a universal cascade utilization method for battery modules, aiming to improve the problem of inconsistent sampling and power interface specifications of different battery module models, based on their make, model, etc. i.e., their provenance.</p>	<p>Two flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-26</p>	<p>CN119395558 (A) Nov 28th 2024 UNIV HEFEI TECHNOLOGY Feb 7th 2025</p>	<p>RETIRED BATTERY RAPID CAPACITY ESTIMATION METHOD BASED ON ELECTROCHEMICAL IMPEDANCE SPECTROSCOPY [EIS] AND PARTIAL DISCHARGE DATA</p> <p>The method for quickly estimating the capacity of a decommissioned battery based on electrochemical impedance spectroscopy [EIS] and partial discharge data, comprises the following steps of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1, carrying out discharge test on a recycled decommissioned battery, and extracting the discharge data of the battery; 2, establishing a constant-current charging time prediction model so as to predict the capacity; and 3, correcting the initial capacity prediction by using the capacity estimation based on the internal resistance so as to realize more accurate battery capacity estimation. <p>According to the method, the capacity of the decommissioned battery can be quickly and accurately estimated, and a reliable basis is provided for recycling and recycling management of the battery.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – One of only a few publications found to disclose the use of EIS and partial discharge data in assessing retired batteries for reuse, recycling, etc..</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is a schematic diagram of the equivalent circuit model of the battery of the present invention.</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER3 – BMS for monitoring and control of batteries in second-life applications from reuse and remanufacture – update

Notes

1. Each of **RECIRC3-21** through **RECIRC3-26** discloses a system that includes a battery management system [BMS] that may be applied to the reuse of retired/decommissioned batteries.
2. **RECIRC3-25** refers to ‘echelon’ utilization of retired batteries. As recorded in the **1st Iteration T-FA**, the Chinese have developed the concept of ‘echelon/cascade battery utilization’. The idea is that batteries in the upper echelons of health are those in use in automotive EVs. Below that is an echelon of batteries that may be reused in EVs that require less power or, perhaps, in power packs for mobile phone towers, greenhouse heating and the like. Finally, there is an echelon that is no longer useful for its power output and is sent for dismantling and recycling/reuse of its component parts.
3. During the course of the RECIORCULATE project, **KER3** has come to be redefined. Our understanding of this change to Task 4.2 – the development of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy [EIS] as part of the battery monitoring system is as follows:

Extract from original Task 4.2: CSEM, based on LBT specification, will develop a next-gen second-life dedicated BMS for LV/HC applications (ideally 48V/300A) and based on high energy cells (>250Wh/cell) already available at LBT. BMS will be based on the zBMS platform and will have the following advanced features: (i) Embedded EIS sensing to continuously sense SOX indicators and monitor each cell states; (ii) bypass and hot-swap capability to increase safety and ease maintenance; (iii) active SOC balancing based on string-current (50% SOC rebalancing capabilities); (iv) SOH balancing and lifetime prolongation >20%.

Issue: CSEM originally developed EIS hardware that operates at cell level that is, while functional, too costly and risks becoming obsolete because new integrated circuits [ICs] from major players can perform EIS at much lower cost and higher efficiency by operating at module level (i.e. several EIS are performed at the same time on all the cells of a battery module).

Status M28: CSEM successfully delivered an off-the-shelf EIS solution, which is technically functional but remains costly. Then, CSEM obtained early IC samples that are being tested meet expectations.

To address this transition, CSEM is proceeding with two iterations of the balancing solution:

- V1 (without EIS IC): balancing-focused solution (currently in progress: the concept was approved by LBT and the schematics are finalized as this report is written. The PCB layout will start mid-September at the latest.
- V2 (with EIS IC): later integration, incorporating updated balancing with the new IC. Collaboration with LBT: requirements and specifications for battery racks reviewed, enabling CSEM to advance on the schematics for V1.

Since the project extension requested to reach V2 was rejected – this is the current plan & objectives to be achieved by M36:

- T4.2: CSEM confirms that they will first produce the V1 prototype (without EIS) and validate it at module level, and, if feasible, at pack level, at their own facilities. They will then produce V2, which is planned for deployment at LBT for TRL 6 validation. Given the tight timeline for V2, CSEM notes that if V2 is delayed, they will use V1 as a fallback for TRL 6 validation at LBT. This means that TRL 6 validation will occur in all cases, using either V1 or V2, ensuring compliance with the GA.

- They will then produce V2, which is planned for deployment at LBT for TRL 6 validation. Given the tight timeline for V2, CSEM notes that if V2 is delayed, they will use V1 as a fallback for TRL 6 validation at LBT. This means that TRL 6 validation will occur in all cases, using either V1 or V2, ensuring compliance with the GA.
- OBJ3: Lifetime Increase KPI: CSEM also confirms that the evaluation of the lifetime increase KPI (OBJ3) will be performed via simulation only, as there won't be time for long-duration cycling. The simulation will be calibrated using V1 experimental results, and if V2 results become available in time, the model will be re-calibrated accordingly.

In light of these changes, [RECIRC3-26](#) is included here as disclosing a VI type EIS monitoring system and each of [RECIRC3-21](#) and [RECIRC3-22](#) is included as disclosing V2 type EIS-based monitoring systems based on ICs.

Overall summary – Six new publications were found that disclose battery management systems [BMSs] for managing the incorporation and reuse of automotive EV batteries in new modules and pack,. Three of these disclose EIS-based monitoring systems that enable non-invasive monitoring of battery SOX characteristics. The disclosures of all of them will have to be taken into account in defining the RECIRCULATE system for that purpose, if the partners wish to protect it by patent.

3.1.4 Systems for battery sorting by SOX and provenance for recycling

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.4 – Patents and patent applications relating to systems for battery sorting by SOX and provenance for recycling			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-32	CN117114659 (A) May 13th 2022 GUIZHOU GUIHANG NEW ENERGY TECH CO LTD CN] Nov 24th 2023	QUICK LITHIUM ION BATTERY RECOVERY SYSTEM BASED ON TWO-DIMENSIONAL CODE RECOGNITION The invention comprises the following elements: 1, a battery identity system data generating a two-dimensional code for identifying a manufacturer and a model on a battery shell ; 2, constructing a battery characteristic data collecting system for battery characteristics corresponding to each battery model; 3, a processing method data sorting out a scrap processing method in a corresponding state according to the battery characteristics collected in 2; 4, battery identity recognition: scanning a battery two-dimensional code, matching manufacturer and battery information, and summarizing to generate a manufacturer processing opinion C1 ; 5, battery performance detection: detecting the performance of the waste battery to generate a detection processing opinion C2 ; 6, scrap treatment: comprehensively treating the suggestions C1 and C2, matching the result with the treatment method in 3, finding out a corresponding scrap treatment method Bx, and treating the scrap battery according to the corresponding scrap treatment method Bx. Updated status No information since Mar 17 th 2024 – fate currently unknown	No particularly informative figure available

<p>RECIRC2-33</p>	<p>CN116823736 (A) Jun 1st 2023 GUANGDONG XIRUI INTELLIGENT TECH CO LTD [CN] Sep 29th 2023</p>	<p>BATTERY BOX INSPECTION METHOD AND DEVICE, STORAGE MEDIUM AND COMPUTER EQUIPMENT</p> <p>The method comprises the steps of:</p> <p>obtaining a product six-view of a to-be-inspected battery box product;</p> <p>performing feature recognition on the six views of the product through a convolutional neural network to obtain surface feature information of each product view in the six views of the product;</p> <p>according to the surface feature information, splitting the corresponding product views to obtain a plurality of fragment images of each product view wherein each segment image corresponds to a unit assembly used for forming a battery box product to be inspected;</p> <p>inputting the plurality of fragment images of each product view into a convolutional neural network classifier to obtain an inspection result output by a convolutional neural network;</p> <p>and</p> <p>if the inspection result is qualified, recording the product information of the to-be-inspected battery box product to a qualified product file;</p> <p>and</p> <p>if the inspection result is unqualified, sending out early warning information.</p> <p>The inspection efficiency of the battery box and the accuracy of the inspection result can be improved.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 1st Office Action – Dec 20th 2025</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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RECIRC3 publications

<p>RECIRC3-27</p>	<p>CN119834392 (A) Nov 28th 2024 ULTRAHIGH PRESSURE COMPANY OF STATE GRID QINGHAI ELECTRIC POWER COMPANY STATE GRID QINGHAI ELECTRIC POWER CO [CN] Apr 15th 2025</p>	<p>RECYCLING SYSTEM OF RETIRED STORAGE BATTERY</p> <p>The system comprises a storage battery performance management and control module which is used for carrying out the internal resistance test and charging and discharging test of the out-of-service storage battery, obtaining the performance data, taking the storage battery with the performance data greater than preset data as a recyclable storage battery, and carrying out the warehousing processing of the recyclable storage battery.</p> <p>The storage battery inventory management module is used for acquiring the model data, the manufacturer data, the commissioning time data and the quantity data of the storage batteries input by the user, taking the data as demand data, carrying out storage battery matching based on the demand data to obtain a target storage battery, and carrying out warehouse-out processing on the target storage battery.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN119834392 (B) – Oct 3rd 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a BMS that includes managing the status of retired batteries and reusing them on demand according to their provenance and capacity.</p>	<p>A flow chart is provided but is annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-28</p>	<p>CN119500617 (A) Jan 21st 2025 ANHUI GUOQI TECH CO LTD [CN] UNIV SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY CHINA [CN] Feb 25th 2025</p>	<p>RETIRED BATTERY SECONDARY SORTING METHOD, SYSTEM AND EQUIPMENT BASED ON RANDOM CHARGING FRAGMENTS AND MEDIUM</p> <p>The system comprises a code scanning module, a charging and discharging control module, a data acquisition module, a data processing module and a sorting module.</p> <p>The method comprises the steps of:</p> <p>generating a single battery identification code, constructing a battery code database, and performing charging and discharging control on a single battery based on a preset charging and discharging strategy;</p> <p>obtaining a time sequence sample data set of temperature, voltage and capacity change, converting the time sequence sample data set into two-dimensional image data and storing the two-dimensional image data, and</p> <p>training a prediction model through a two-dimensional convolutional neural network [CNN] to estimate the maximum available capacity of the battery so as to realize secondary sorting of the battery.</p> <p>The method can reduce test time and energy consumption, improve battery sorting efficiency and precision, reduce memory occupation and rear-end model operation time, and is suitable for efficient and accurate sorting of retired batteries.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN119500617 (B) – Apr 29th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses sorting of EoL batteries using artificial intelligence [AI] and including sorting by battery ID code i.e., by provenance.</p>	<p>Five flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-25</p>	<p>CN120389139 (A) May 6th 2025 JIANGSU HUAYOU ENERGY TECH CO LTD [CN] Jul 29th 2025</p>	<p>UNIVERSAL ECHELON UTILIZATION METHOD FOR BATTERY MODULES</p> <p>The invention relates to the technical field of battery management, and discloses a battery module general echelon utilization method, which comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, carrying out performance detection on a retired battery module;</p> <p>S2, connecting the battery module to the echelon utilization system through the lossless access device;</p> <p>S3, integrating a module-level battery management module in each battery module;</p> <p>S4, arranging a direct current-direct current conversion module in each module;</p> <p>S5, a system-level battery management module is arranged on the battery system level; and</p> <p>S6, when the module has a fault, isolating the fault module through the system-level battery management module.</p> <p>According to the invention, through the standardized design of the sampling interface and the power interface, and in combination with a lossless access technology, universal access of battery modules with different models, specifications and performances is realized.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a universal cascade utilization method for battery modules, aiming to improve the problem of inconsistent sampling and power interface specifications of different battery module models, based on their make, model, etc. i.e., their provenance.</p>	<p>Two flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-29</p>	<p>CN120912193 (A) Oct 9th 2025 NANJING FUCHUANG BIG DATA IND DEVELOPMENT CO LTD [CN] Nov 7th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY DECOMMISSIONING AND RECYCLING QUALITY TRACEABILITY AND GRADING TREATMENT SYSTEM AND METHOD</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>obtaining data, and carrying out the preprocessing of the data;</p> <p>a forward electrochemical model is constructed and solved, a short-time high-temperature event is obtained, and a thermal damage risk value is output;</p> <p>based on multi-mode non-destructive detection, external boundary measurement is collected, and chemical non-uniformity is output through a multi-mode coupling strategy;</p> <p>the recovery measurement, the thermal damage risk value and the chemical non-uniformity are standardized into recovery verification labels, abstract hash is calculated, and a timestamp is submitted; and</p> <p>the output and the battery recovery multi-dimensional indexes are fused into a comprehensive disposal score, disposal suggestions for each batch are output according to a set rule, and sorting and execution instructions are issued;</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN120912193 (B) – Dec 2nd 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of a lifecycle data access module to acquire data from battery digital twin [DT] archives, battery management systems [BMSs], IoT platforms, recycling centres and automated dismantling lines, and to clean, fill in missing data, align time and granularity, and map unique identifiers to the data, in pursuit of a method for quality traceability and graded disposal of retired batteries.</p>	<p>Two flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER4 – Process definition for faster and more accurate sorting by SOX and battery provenance (including the cathode and anode materials) for recycling

Each of [RECIRC3-25](#) and [RECIRC3-27](#), [RECIRC3-28](#) and [RECIRC3-29](#) discloses the sorting of retired EV batteries according to their SOX characteristics and their provenance

Overall summary – Whereas in the searches for the [2nd Iteration T-FA](#), no patent publications were found that disclose the use of provenance in the sorting of retired batteries, in the searches for this [3rd Iteration T-FA](#), four publications were found to do so. The teachings of each will have to be taken into account, should the partners decide to protect their own developments in this technology area by patent.

3.1.5 Smart/safe shipping/storage solutions for 2nd life batteries

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.5 – Patents and patent applications relating to smart/safe shipping/storage solutions for 2 nd life batteries			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-37	KR20240036393 (A) Sep 13th 2022 MTEK INFORMATION TECH CO LTD [KR] Mar 20th 2024	<p>VEHICLE WASTE BATTERY PACK STORAGE DEVICE</p> <p>Extract – The purpose of the present invention is to provide a vehicle waste battery pack storage device capable of more safely storing a battery pack separated from an electric vehicle and measuring the status of a battery module without separating the battery module from the battery pack. A vehicle waste battery pack storage device (100) comprises a main body (200) having a storage space provided inside so that a vehicle waste battery pack having a battery module (12) can be stored, and a status measurement unit (300) that measures status information of the battery module (12) such as the cell’s impedance, internal resistance, voltage or current and can also calculate the charge amount, i.e., the remaining power amount, based on information such as the measured voltage or current</p> <p>The display panel (320) is installed on the front of the combination cover (220) and outputs measurement information measured by the measurement module (310).</p> <p>Updated status Granted as KR102766883 (B1) – Feb 13th 2025</p>	

<p>RECIRC2-38</p>	<p>CN116553004 (A) Jun 26th 2023 DONGFENG MOTOR GROUP CO LTD [CN] Aug 8th 2023</p>	<p>PROTECTIVE DEVICE AND BATTERY MODULE</p> <p>The invention discloses a protection device and a battery module, and solves the technical problem that valuables are easy to damage when being influenced by external force or collided in the prior art, the protection device comprises a protection box, a collection bin and a buffer mechanism, and the protection box is provided with a protection cavity; the collection bin is movably arranged in the protection cavity, and a plurality of mounting grooves for placing objects are formed in the collection bin; the buffering mechanism is movably installed in the protection box and comprises a first elastic piece, a second elastic piece, a buffering strip and a buffering plate, and the first elastic piece acts on the buffering plate so that the buffering plate can conduct elastic buffering in the first direction; the two or more buffer strips are located on the upper side and the lower side of the collecting bin correspondingly and are in sliding connection with the collecting bin in the second direction perpendicular to the first direction; the second elastic piece acts on the buffering strip so that the buffering strip can conduct elastic buffering in the third direction perpendicular to the first direction and the second direction. The protection box is buffered through the buffer mechanism, and the stress of the collection bin is reduced.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 1st Office Action – Jan 12th 2026</p>	<p>100-protection device; 110-protection box, 111-collection bin, 112-installation slot, 113-first slide slot, 115-limiting bar; 120-buffer mechanism, 121-buffer plate, 122-first elastic member, 123-second elastic member, 124-buffer bar, 125-first slider, 126-fixing rod, 127-limiting hole, 128-fixed bar, 129-limiting rod, 140-pull rod; 200-battery pack.</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-39</p>	<p>CN117022872 (A) Aug 8th 2023 XIAMEN FENGHUO INTERACTIVE TECH CO LTD [CN] Nov 10th 2023</p>	<p>EXPLOSION-PROOF CABINET FOR POWER BATTERY</p> <p>Extract – The explosion-proof cabinet comprises a cabinet body and an automatic fire extinguishing device.</p> <p>The working principle of the present invention is:</p> <p>When the power battery A needs to be transported and stored, the power battery A is placed in the cabinet body 11 of the cabinet and at least one power battery A presses down the water storage bag, and then the cabinet body 11 and the cabinet cover 12 are connected by the buckle 12 to close the cabinet body 11.</p> <p>When the power battery A placed in the cabinet body 11 catches fire, the temperature inside the cabinet body 1 rises and causes the fire sprinkler heads 221 to burst. The downward pressure of the power battery A on the water storage bag 21 will transport the fire extinguishing water source inside the water storage bag 21 to the fire sprinkler heads 221 and spray it out from the fire sprinkler heads 221, thereby automatically extinguishing the fire of the power battery A.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 1st Office Action – Apr 14th 2025</p>	
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<p>RECIRC2-40</p>	<p>CN117416625 (A) Nov 14th 2023 HUNAN ZHENGYUAN ENERGY STORAGE MAT AND DEVICE INSTITUTE [CN] Jan 19th 2024</p>	<p>SAFE TRANSPORTATION SYSTEM FOR WASTE BATTERIES</p> <p>The invention discloses a waste battery safe transportation system which comprises a box body, a box cover and a fire extinguishing device, the box body comprises a bottom plate and a side surrounding plate, the bottom plate and the side surrounding plate define a containing cavity used for containing waste batteries, a first airflow control component is arranged on the side surrounding plate, the box body is further connected with a gas cylinder, and the gas cylinder is connected with the box cover. The gas cylinder is filled with non-combustible gas, the gas cylinder is communicated with the box body through a gas pipeline, and the gas pipeline is provided with a second gas flow control component.</p> <p>According to the safe transportation system for the waste batteries, through the design that the fire extinguishing device is arranged and the gas cylinder is connected, the dual fire extinguishing protection effect is achieved, the temperature, the gas pressure and the combustible gas concentration can be monitored, the positioning and remote data transmission functions are achieved, the mobility of equipment is good, and safety is high.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 2nd Office Action – Jul 18th 2025</p>	<p>1. Box body; 2. Box cover; 3. Fire extinguishing device; 4. First airflow control component; 5. Display instrument; 6. Intelligent control panel; 7. Sensor; 8. Gas cylinder; 9. Gas pipeline; 10. Second airflow control component.</p>
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<p>RECIRC2-41</p>	<p>CN117699208 (A) Dec 13th 2023 SUZHOU KUNCHENG IND EQUIPMENT CO LTD [CN] Mar 15th 2024</p>	<p>SQUARE BATTERY CELL TRANSPORT CASE STRUCTURE WITH INNER AND OUTER DOUBLE-LAYER PACKAGING CASE BODIES</p> <p>The square battery cell transport case structure comprises the outer-layer packaging box body, the inner-layer packaging box body is arranged in the outer-layer packaging box body, the inner-layer packaging box body comprises a bottom support tray, an inner cover and middle lining trays, a plurality of stacked middle lining trays are arranged between the bottom support tray and the inner cover, a plurality of first positioning grooves with upward openings are formed in the surfaces of the middle lining trays, second positioning grooves with downward openings are formed in the back surfaces of the middle lining trays, and the inner-layer packaging box body is arranged in the middle lining trays. The upper sides of the square battery cells on one layer of middle lining tray are inserted into the second positioning grooves in the back surface of the upper layer of middle lining tray, first grooves corresponding to electrode columns of the square battery cells in position are formed in the bottom surfaces of the second positioning grooves, a communication groove is formed between every two adjacent second positioning grooves, and middle vent holes arranged in an array are further formed in the surfaces of the middle lining trays. Compared with the prior art, the battery cell is fully positioned and protected, and rusting caused by water drops condensed on the surface of the battery cell and the surface of the electrode column is avoided.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 1st Office Action – Feb 11th 2026</p>	<p>1. Outer packaging box; 11. Bottom support; 111. Enclosure edge; 112. Tray positioning block; 113. Support foot; 1131. Through hole; 12. Enclosure; 13. Upper cover; 131. Boss; 1311. Strapping belt positioning groove; 1312. Support block; 14. Fixing belt; 2. Inner packaging box; 21. Bottom support tray; 22. Inner cover; 221. Upper vent; 222. Desiccant placement groove; 23. Middle lining tray; 231. First positioning groove; 232. Second positioning groove; 2321. First groove; 2322. Connecting groove; 233. Middle vent; 234. First positioning block; 235. Second positioning block; 236. First slot; 9. Square battery cell.</p>
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RECIRC3 publications

<p>RECIRC3-07</p>	<p>CN120840404 (A) Apr 26th 2024 CHINA RESOURCES MICROELECTRONICS CHONGQING CO LTD [CN] Oct 28th 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY HEAT ENERGY EARLY WARNING CONTROL METHOD AND SYSTEM AND NEW ENERGY VEHICLE</p> <p>The method comprises the steps that</p> <p>(1) a feedback current matrix of a battery module is set;</p> <p>(2) controlling charging and discharging of the battery module based on the feedback current matrix, and performing temperature control on the battery pack based on the environment temperature;</p> <p>(3) in the process of the step (2), training and updating the SOC curve local model, fitting the SOC curve, judging that the SOC curve is normal when the SOC curve converges, judging that the SOC curve is abnormal when the SOC curve diverges, and sending out a first early warning signal; meanwhile, monitoring the temperature rise of the battery module, judging that the battery module is normal when the temperature rise speed is less than a third preset value, and judging that the module is abnormal when the temperature rise speed is greater than or equal to the third preset value; when the first early warning signal and the second early warning signal are both effective, charging and discharging are stopped, and fault early warning is sent out; and</p> <p>(4) in the process of the step (2), if the working state exceeds the safety protection range, fire extinguishing and explosion prevention measures are started.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comments – Discloses an explosion-safe management system based on SOC. Application of the derived safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-08</p>	<p>CN118688683 (A) May 20th 2024 UNIV NORTH CHINA ELECTYRIC POWER [CN] Sep 24th 2024</p>	<p>BATTERY SAFETY STATE QUANTIFICATION METHOD AND SYSTEM CONSIDERING BATTERY LIFE</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>arranging a plurality of sensors for monitoring the state parameters of the battery in real time in an energy storage system, and storing the collected state parameter data in a database;</p> <p>constructing a battery state of safety [SOS] quantization function, wherein the battery SOS quantization function and the charge state have the same numerical range; and quantifying the battery SOS of the energy storage system by using the battery SOS quantification function.</p> <p>Compared with the prior art, according to the technical scheme, the quantitative expression mode of the SOS of the battery is scientifically constructed, multiple battery parameters are comprehensively considered, comprehensive and accurate evaluation of the SOS of the battery of the energy storage system is achieved, potential safety hazards can be found in time, accidents are avoided, and the method has good application prospects.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of multiple sensors in determining the real time SOS of a battery pack. Application of the derived safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>Three flow charts are provided but are annotated in Chinese only</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-30</p>	<p>CN118458150 (A) Jun 4th 2024 BEICHEN ADVANCED CYCLE TECH QINGDAO CO LTD [CN] Aug 9th 2024</p>	<p>SAFE STORAGE AND TRANSPORTATION DEVICE FOR RETIRED POWER LITHIUM BATTERIES</p> <p>The transportation box is internally provided with a first placement area for placing a battery storage mechanism and a second placement area for placing a cooling and fire extinguishing mechanism; and the cooling and fire extinguishing mechanism is connected with the battery storage mechanism and is used for cooling or extinguishing the batteries stored in the battery storage mechanism.</p> <p>According to the safe storage and transportation device for the retired power lithium batteries, the cooling and fire extinguishing mechanism is arranged in the second placement area of the transportation box, so that cooling treatment or fire extinguishing treatment can be conveniently carried out on the lithium batteries when the temperature of the lithium batteries is too high or the lithium batteries are on fire, and emergency situations in the transportation process of the lithium batteries are effectively treated.</p> <p>The risk range of the decommissioned power lithium battery during storage and transportation is reduced, the liquid nitrogen can effectively control ignition of the battery, and the safety of the decommissioned power lithium battery in the storage and transportation process is guaranteed.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses one of many examples of the suppression of fires due to retired LIBs, should they arise during transportation – in this case using liquid nitrogen.</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is an internal structural diagram of the safe transportation device provided in an embodiment of the present invention.</p> <p>1. Transport box; 2. Battery storage mechanism; 3. First placement area; 4. Cooling and fire extinguishing mechanism; 9. Buckle; 10. Movable door panel; 11. Fixing foot; 12. Electrical system control cabinet; 13. Third placement area.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-09</p>	<p>CN118859007 (A) Jun 24th 2024 HEFEI GUOXUAN HIGH TECH POWER ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Oct 29th 2024</p>	<p>BATTERY PACK INTERNAL GAS CONTENT MONITORING METHOD AND APPLICATION THEREOF</p> <p>The detection method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, aging a battery to enable the battery to enter a specific SOH state;</p> <p>S2, putting the aged battery into a closed gas tank, and opening an anti-explosion valve of the battery in a triggering manner; and</p> <p>S3, performing chromatographic analysis on the gas in the gas tank, and establishing a database of the content of the gas in the battery.</p> <p>According to the method, a battery pack thermal runaway gas content database is established by monitoring the variety and content change trend of gas released by the battery in the process from different use working conditions to valve opening, and thermal runaway can be warned to a certain extent by subsequently monitoring the real-time change of gas in the battery pack.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses means for identifying and detecting the concentration of gases that might lead to thermal runaway of battery packs. A database is developed that allows prediction of runaway events and that informs a triggering of an explosion-proof valve. To prevent inflammable gas build up. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is a schematic diagram of the gas tank part of the present invention;</p> <p>In the diagram: 1. Gas tank; 2. Gas chromatograph; 3. Piping; 4. Valve; 5. Return gas pipe; 6. Collection tube; 7. Air bag.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-31</p>	<p>CN119059110 (A) Sep 11th 2024 HEFEI HENGXIN LIGHTWEIGHT TECH DEVELOPMENT CO LTD [CN] Dec 3rd 2024</p>	<p>TRAY DEVICE FOR BATTERY TRANSPORTATION</p> <p>The tray device comprises a transportation frame, a plurality of loading boxes distributed at intervals are arranged in the transportation frame, butt joint assemblies are arranged between the loading boxes and the transportation frame, the top of each loading box is open, a movably connected bearing plate is arranged in each loading box, and the vertical section of each bearing plate is concave.</p> <p>The battery is inserted into the bearing plate and is wrapped by the bearing plate, foaming layers are arranged on the opposite faces in the bearing box, the side faces, close to the bearing plate, of the foaming layers are movably attached to the outer wall of the battery, the foaming layers and the bearing plate are made of expanded polypropylene [EPP] materials, and movable covering assemblies are arranged in the bearing plate and the loading box.</p> <p>Finally, the movable covering assembly is used for positioning the battery, so that the damage to the battery in the battery assembling and mounting process is effectively avoided, and meanwhile, the safety of the battery in the transportation process is improved.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of EPP materials to prevent physical damage to batteries during transportation. Application to carriage of retired batteries is not specifically disclosed but must be obvious to ‘the ordinary person skilled in the art’.</p>	<p>FIG. 1 is a schematic diagram of the overall structure of the present invention.</p> <p>1. Transportation rack; 5. Partitions; 6. Positioning strips; 17. Sealing door; 20. Pressure plate</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-32</p>	<p>CN120003858 (A) Apr 10th 2025 YAMEI SANXIONG GUANGDONG TECH CO LTD [CN] May 16th 2025</p>	<p>NEW ENERGY BATTERY PACKAGING BOX</p> <p>The invention discloses a new energy battery packaging box which comprises a bottom support, a cover body, a first reinforcing structure and a second reinforcing structure, the cover body and the bottom support are detachably connected, a containing cavity is formed between the cover body and the bottom support and used for containing a new energy battery, and the first reinforcing structure is arranged on the cover body; the second reinforcing structure is arranged on the bottom support.</p> <p>According to the technical scheme, the new energy battery packaging box can improve the transportation safety of new energy batteries.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a packaging box designed to o prevent physical damage to LIBs and battery packs during transportation. Application to carriage of retired batteries is not specifically disclosed but must be obvious to ‘the ordinary person skilled in the art’.</p>	<p>10. Cover; 11. Upper cover; 12. Lower cover; 121. Rib; 13. Second support leg; 131. Limiting protrusion; 14. Receiving cavity; 20. Base support; 21. First tray; 211. Second rib; 22. Second tray; 221. Third rib; 23. First support leg; 231. Limiting groove; 24. Limiting part; 30. First reinforcing structure; 31. First reinforcing rod; 40. Second reinforcing structure; 32. Second reinforcing rod; 50. Sealing gasket; 60. Second flexible gasket; 70. New energy battery.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-33</p>	<p>CN119916228 (A) Apr 22nd 2025 SICHUAN ENGINEERING TECHNICAL UNIV [CN] May 2nd 2025</p>	<p>EVALUATION METHOD AND EVALUATION SYSTEM FOR CHARGING SAFETY OF RETIRED LITHIUM BATTERY</p> <p>The evaluation method for the charging safety of the decommissioned lithium battery comprises the following steps:</p> <p>acquiring surface temperature data of the decommissioned lithium battery, a brand new lithium battery and an end-of-life lithium battery under a plurality of charging current working conditions; extracting characteristic values of the surface temperature data of the retired lithium battery, the brand new lithium battery and the end-of-life lithium battery under all charging current working conditions; calculating a single safety risk coefficient of the retired lithium battery under a specific charging current working condition; calculating a comprehensive safety risk coefficient of the retired lithium battery under all charging current working conditions; and different safety levels are divided, and charging current limiting values are correspondingly given.</p> <p>According to the invention, a plurality of batteries with the same safety level can be recombined, so that the control management of the recombined battery pack is facilitated, the consistency and safety of the recombined battery pack are improved, the service life is prolonged, and the probability of thermal runaway is reduced.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Granted as CN119916228 (B) – Jul 4th 2025</p> <p>Comment – Discloses safety assessment of multiple retired batteries with a view to recombining them in a new pack with an optimized output and safety level. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 3 shows a schematic diagram of the circuit connection of the charging data acquisition module in this invention;</p> <p>1-Charging data acquisition module, 6-Retired lithium battery, 7-New lithium battery, 8-End-of-Life [EoL] lithium battery</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-12</p>	<p>CN119864528 (A) Jan 16th 2025 BAISHITONG ZHEJIANG SAFETY TECH CO LTD [CN] Apr 22nd 2025</p>	<p>BATTERY RISK EARLY WARNING MANAGEMENT AND CONTROL SYSTEM AND METHOD</p> <p>The invention provides a battery risk early warning management and control system that comprises a weak grating temperature sensor, a weak grating vibration sensor, an optical fiber grating hydrogen concentration sensor, an optical fiber signal demodulator, a gas filling module, a gas pressure detection module, a risk early warning module, a remote terminal and a management and control module. The weak grating temperature and vibration sensor and the fiber Bragg grating hydrogen concentration sensor are used for sensing the temperature, the vibration condition and the released hydrogen concentration generated due to the abnormal safety and health state of the battery in the battery pack.</p> <p>The risk early warning module carries out early warning reminding according to risk data, and the gas filling module is used for filling nitrogen into the battery pack. And when the gas pressure detection module detects that the air pressure in the battery pack exceeds the standard, the lead seal automatically falls off.</p> <p>According to the system, the inert gas is filled into the battery pack, and the battery temperature, the vibration condition and the hydrogen concentration are monitored in real time by virtue of the sensor to perform risk management and control, so that the battery is effectively prevented from fire explosion.</p> <p>Status Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses the use of nitrogen in suppressing thermal runaway of batteries in a pack. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 2 is an internal structural diagram of the battery risk warning and control system according to an embodiment of the present invention;</p> <p>Reference numerals: 1. Weak grating temperature detection module; 11. Weak grating temperature sensor; 2. Weak grating vibration detection module; 21. Weak grating vibration sensor; 3. Fiber Bragg grating gas concentration detection module; 31. Fiber Bragg grating gas concentration sensor; 4. Fiber optic signal demodulator; 41. Photodetector; 42. Data analysis unit; 5. Gas filling module; 6. Gas pressure detection module; 7. Early warning module; 8. Remote terminal; 9. Control module; 10. Fiber optic cable.</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-19</p>	<p>CN120629978 (A) Jul 25th 2025 UNIV ZHEJIANG TECHNOLOGY RUIPU LANJUN ENERGY CO LTD [CN] Sep 12th 2025</p>	<p>LITHIUM ION BATTERY SAFETY STATE ESTIMATION METHOD BASED ON WORKING CONDITION FRAGMENT CHARACTERISTICS AND UNSUPERVISED CLUSTERING</p> <p>The method comprises the steps:</p> <p>achieving the segmentation of different working condition data based on K-means based on an MIT-Stanford mixed working condition cycle data set;</p> <p>for the segmentation data, segment safety features and global safety features of the constant current charging stage, the constant voltage charging stage and the constant current discharging stage are extracted respectively;</p> <p>performing normalization, direction unification, dimension reduction and correlation screening processing on a data set formed by feature extraction in sequence, and combining to generate a plurality of feature data sets;</p> <p>aiming at a plurality of security feature sets, adopting a particle swarm optimization [PSO] algorithm to optimize fuzzy C-means [FCM] clustering center selection, introducing GG distance measurement to replace Euclidean distance, and establishing an SOS estimation method based on PSO-fuzzy clustering;</p> <p>independently clustering each feature set, giving a 0/1 score according to different clustering center results; and finally aggregating a good reputation rate as an SOS estimated value.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Under examination</p> <p>Comment – Discloses use of a a particle swarm optimization [PSO] algorithm to optimize fuzzy C-means [FCM] clustering center selection for estimation of battery SOS. Application of the safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs is not specifically disclosed.</p>	<p>FIG. 6 Based on the PCC analysis results between the filtered features, three features in each group (with $PCC \leq 0.7$) were selected and combined. Features were allowed to be reused to cover complete information, and finally 107 feature groups were generated to provide input for PSO-GG clustering.</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER5 – Smart/safe shipping/storage solution for second-life batteries

On the one hand, each of [RECIRC3-07](#) through [RECIRC3-09](#), [RECIRC3-12](#), [RECIRC3-19](#) and [RECIRC3-33](#) discloses means for ensuring the safety of batteries. Of these, only, [RECIRC3-19](#) discloses the use of artificial intelligence [AI] in creating a smart SOS estimation system for (retired) batteries. None of them discloses the application of its safety system to transportation of batteries, modules or packs.

On the other hand, each of [RECIRC3-30](#) through [RECIRC3-32](#) discloses means for securing (retired) batteries against physical damage during transportation but not their combination with on-board safety systems to suppress thermal runaway and/or explosions..

Overall summary – No patent publication was found that discloses a battery safety system combined with a smart container for the storage and/or transportation of retired batteries, modules or packs. Moreover, no publication was found that discloses adaptation of such transport means to specific trucks – such as is proposed for DHL’s trucks in the RECIRCULATE project.

3.1.6 Blockchain-backed systems for trading of batteries and parts for 2nd life applications

RECIRCULATE – Table 3.1.6 – Patents and patent applications relating to blockchain-backed systems for trading of batteries and parts for 2 nd life applications			
Report Ref #	Publication # Priority date Applicants/Assignees Publication date	TITLE Abstract/extract Updated status/Status	Figure (s) Extract (s)
RECIRC2 patent applications not granted in time for the 2nd Iteration T=FA report with Updated status			
RECIRC2-42	WO2024063393 (A1) Sep 20th 2022 AIZEN GLOBAL CO INC [KR] Mar 28th 2024	BATTERY HISTORY MANAGEMENT METHOD AND DEVICE FOR PERFORMING SAME The present invention relates to a battery history management method and a device for performing same. The battery history management method may include the steps in which: a battery history management device generates a battery non-fungible token (NFT) on the basis of a blockchain; and the battery history management device generates battery value evaluation data corresponding to the battery NFT to record the battery value evaluation data on the blockchain. Updated status Granted so far as: KR102588446 (B1) – Oct 13th 2023 US12523701 (B2) – Jan 13th 2026	No particularly informative figure available

<p>RECIRC2-06</p>	<p>CN116520149 (A) Jan 31st 2023 JIANGSU WEIHENG INTELLIGENT TECH CO LTD [CN] Aug 1st 2023</p>	<p>REAL-TIME STATE MONITORING METHOD FOR DISTRIBUTED ENERGY STORAGE BATTERY</p> <p>The real-time state monitoring method comprises the following steps:</p> <p>S1, constructing an alliance block chain;</p> <p>S2, calculating and storing the state of the battery through a BMS (Battery Management System);</p> <p>S3, the BMS communicates with the Internet of Things equipment, and sends the state information obtained in the S2 to the Internet of Things equipment;</p> <p>S4, uploading the information on the Internet of Things equipment to a block chain, and storing the information in a shared database of an operation and maintenance provider;</p> <p>S5, the alliance block chain provides a public key and a private key for the node user, and the node user can access the shared database of the block chain through the public key to obtain the state information of the battery.</p> <p>According to the monitoring method, programs are accessed and transacted with other node users through a private key, monitoring parameters of the energy storage battery comprise SOC, SOH, SOP, SOE, SOT and SOS, and meanwhile, the timeliness and the safety of data are improved through linkage of the Internet of Things and a block chain technology.</p> <p>Updated status Rejected at 2nd Office Action – Nov 7th 2025</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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RECIRC3 publications

RECIRC3-34

WO2023127602 (A1)

Dec 27th 2021

DENSO CORP [JP]

Jul 6th 2023

BATTERY-MONITORING SYSTEM

In the present invention, battery monitoring comprises:

a monitoring unit (20) that monitors a battery that can be charged and discharged; and

a host device (50) to which monitoring data obtained via monitoring of the battery by the monitoring unit is provided, said host device (50) storing at least a portion of specific information included in the monitoring data using a blockchain.

The host device has: a block-generating unit (53) that generates a new block including at least a portion of the specific information and a hash value based on the final block connected last in the block chain; and

an external communication device (55) for distributing and saving new blocks generated by the block-generating unit to a plurality of external devices.

At least one of the monitoring unit and the host device is provided with data protection units (24, 56) for ensuring the reliability of the monitoring data.

Status

Granted so far as **EP4459590 (B1)** – Feb 11th 2026

Comment – Discloses a blockchain-based monitoring system designed, *inter alia*, to prevent unauthorized access to the battery’s manufacturing and operational history.

RECIRC3-35

US20240221436 (A1)

Dec 29th 2022

VOLVO CAR CORP
[SE]

Jul 4th 2024

TRACKING VEHICLE BATTERY CONDITION HISTORY USING BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY

Techniques are described for tracking information regarding the condition history of a vehicle battery using blockchain technology. In an example embodiment, a system comprises a memory that stores computer executable components, and a processor that executes the computer executable components stored in the memory.

The computer executable components comprise a communication component that receives battery information regarding a condition of a vehicle battery over a period of time prior to installation of the vehicle battery in a vehicle, and a recording component that records the vehicle battery information in a blockchain stored on a blockchain network as the vehicle battery information is received over the period of time.

Status

Granted as **US12340635 (B2)** – Jun 24th 2025

Comment – One of at least six applications from **VOLVO CAR CORP [SE]** relating to use of blockchain technology in recording the life history of batteries **before** installation in their EVs. This example is included here as one of those applications that has been granted – despite its similarity to their patent listed below.

RECIRC3-36

US20240222715 (A1)

Dec 29th 2022

VOLVO CAR CORP
[SE]

Jul 4th 2024

INTELLIGENT VEHICLE WITH BLOCKCHAIN CONNECTIVITY

Techniques are described for tracking information regarding the condition history of a vehicle battery using blockchain technology.

In an example embodiment, a system comprises a vehicle battery, and one or more sensors integrated on or within the vehicle battery that capture sensor data regarding a condition of the vehicle battery over a period of time prior to installation of the vehicle battery within a vehicle.

The vehicle battery further comprises a communication component that sends the sensor data to a remote device in response to capture of the sensor data by the one or more sensors.

In various implementations, the remote device comprises a blockchain device part of a blockchain network, and wherein the remote device records the sensor data using the blockchain network.

Status

Granted as US12321888 (B2) – Jun 3rd 2025

Comment – One of at least six applications from **VOLVO CAR CORP [SE]** relating to use of blockchain technology in recording the life history of batteries **before** installation in their EVs. This example is included here as one of those applications that has been granted – despite its similarity to their patent listed above.

<p>RECIRC3-37</p>	<p>KR102787260 (B1) Nov 28th 2023 BLOCKODYSSEY INC [KR] Mar 31st 2025</p>	<p>METHOD FOR MANAGING SECONDARY BATTERY USING BLOCKCHAIN AND APPARATUS FOR PERFORMING THE METHOD</p> <p>According to one embodiment of the present invention, a method for managing secondary battery history using a blockchain may include a step in which a battery history management unit of a battery distribution history management device manages battery production history information, battery use history information, and battery recycling history information, and a step in which a blockchain unit of the battery distribution history management device stores the battery production history information, battery use history information, and battery recycling history information on a blockchain.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Patent granted in Korea only.</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a blockchain-based system for proving use and transferring value for the production/distribution history of batteries in the secondary battery recycling value chain, thereby enabling transparent and safe battery history management.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure provided</p>
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<p>RECIRC3-38</p>	<p>KR102921847 (B1) Nov 18th 2024 K.D.M. TECH CO LTD [KR] Feb 4th 2026</p>	<p>BLOCKCHAIN-BASED WASTE BATTERY DIAGNOSIS SYSTEM</p> <p>In accordance with one embodiment of the present invention, a waste battery diagnosis system comprises:</p> <p>a diagnostic case having a transparent square box structure and accommodating a waste battery;</p> <p>a 3D X-ray photographing device that photographs the accommodated waste battery to generate a 3D X-ray image of the waste battery;</p> <p>a charging and discharging unit that charges and discharges the waste battery and measures parameters including internal resistance, open circuit voltage, charging current, and discharging current of the waste battery;</p> <p>a thermal imaging device that photographs the waste battery during charging and discharging to generate a thermal image;</p> <p>a waste battery diagnosis unit that generates diagnostic information including whether there is a structural abnormality of the waste battery, whether a short circuit has occurred, and an SOH value using the 3D X-ray image, the thermal image, and the parameters; and</p> <p>a blockchain network that propagates a block in which the diagnostic information is recorded to a plurality of nodes that have participated in advance so as to be connected to a previous block according to a consensus algorithm.</p> <p>Status</p> <p>Patent granted in Korea only.</p> <p>Comment – Discloses a box for X-ray and thermal imaging of retired batteries to determine their potential for recycling and for transmitting the imaging data to a blockchain network.</p>	<p>No particularly informative figure available</p>
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Summary of the SotA regarding KER6 – Blockchain-backed marketplace prototype (TRL8) for trusted trading of batteries and related components for reuse, remanufacture or recycling

Each of **RECIRC3-34** through **RECIRC3-37** discloses blockchain-based means for secure recording of the history of the manufacture and use of batteries both before and after installation in EVs,

RECIRC3-38 differs from the others in that it discloses blockchain-based means for secure recording of X-ray-derived and thermal images generated in assessment of SOX characteristics of retired batteries.

Overall summary – From the results of the searches carried out for this **3rd Iteration T-FA**, the same conclusion can be reached as in the report on the **2nd Iteration T-FA** namely that: “The concept of a blockchain-based transaction/trading system for used EV batteries is not novel and the partners in the RECIRCULATE project will have to take into account the teachings of all of the publications listed in **Table 3.1.6**, and more, when they design their own system, particularly if they want to seek patent protection for it.”

3.2. Overall summary of the SotA for each KER

Below are collated the overall summaries from **Section 3.1.1** through **Section 3.1.6** regarding the SotA for each KER.

KER1 – Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

The same conclusion can be reached here as in the report for the **2nd Iteration T-FA** namely that : “From the analysis of publications disclosing means for measuring battery SOH, SOC, SOS, etc., it is obvious that this is a saturated patent landscape and that the beneficiaries will have to create a system that is highly novel and deeply non-obvious should they wish to patent their own approach(es) to such measurements. In addition, they will have to take all the teachings of the listed publications, and more, into account when submitting any patent application of their own.” It may also be concluded that Chinese enterprises continue to be the main competitors for the RECIRCULATE partners in this technology sphere.

KER2 – Validated AI-backed control process for automated pack to module and module to cell dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

No patent or patent application was found that discloses application of AI to the process of disassembling retired/waste EV battery packs or modules, whether by robot or not.

KER3 – BMS for monitoring and control of batteries in second-life applications from reuse and remanufacture – update

Six new publications were found that disclose battery management systems [BMSs] for managing (reused) automotive EV batteries in new modules and packs,. Three of these disclose EIS-based monitoring systems that enable non-invasive monitoring of battery SOX characteristics. The disclosures of all of them will have to be taken into account in defining the RECIRCULATE system for that purpose, if the partners wish to protect it by patent.

KER4 – Process definition for faster and more accurate sorting by SoX and battery provenance (including the cathode and anode materials) for recycling

Whereas in the searches for the **2nd Iteration T-FA**, no patent publications were found that disclose the use of provenance in the sorting of retired batteries, in the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA**, four publications were found to do so. The teachings of each will have to be taken into account, should the partners decide to protect their own developments in this technology area by patent.

KER5 – Smart/safe shipping/storage solution for second-life batteries

No patent publication was found that discloses a battery safety system combined with a smart container for the storage and/or transportation of retired batteries, modules or packs. Moreover, no publication was found that discloses adaptation of such transport means to specific trucks – such as is proposed for DHL’s trucks in the RECIRCULATE project.

KER6 – Blockchain-backed marketplace prototype (TRL8) for trusted trading of batteries and related components for reuse, remanufacture or recycling

From the results of the searches carried out for this **3rd Iteration T-FA**, the same conclusion can be reached as in the report on the **2nd Iteration T-FA** namely that: “The concept of a blockchain-based transaction/trading system for used EV batteries is not novel and the partners in the RECIRCULATE project will have to take into account the teachings of all of the publications listed in **Table 3.1.6**, and more, when they design their own system, particularly if they want to seek patent protection for it.”

Additional notes

One important aspect of the proposed RECIRCULATE system is that the SOH of the retired batteries should be assessed very rapidly. No publication was found that emphasises the speed of battery SOH assessment.

A large percentage of the publications listed in **Table 3.1.1** through **Table 3.1.6** are from Chinese enterprises and are for Chinese national patents or national utility model patents. This means that, so long as they do not attempt to launch any related product on Chinese markets, the partners cannot infringe the IPRs in the inventions disclosed in those publications. However, the teachings of all of them now form part of the prior art and must be taken into account should the partners decide to seek patent protection for their own inventions arising during the RECIRCULATE project.

4. Means of protection for the RECIRCULATE project results

4.1 Protection of technical intellectual property rights [IPRs]

The following table shows the types of IPRs that are relevant to the technical results of a project like RECIRCULATE:

	Patents	Utility Models	Trade Marks	Copyright
What is protected	Technical inventions	Technical inventions	Marks for products & services	Creative works
Required characteristics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New • Inventive • Capable of industrial application 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New • Inventive • Capable of industrial application • Protectable subject matter can be restricted) 	2D or 3D pictures, words, names colours or sounds	Design documents, software, books, databases, songs, semiconductor designs, paintings & photographs
Period of protection	20 years (in most jurisdictions)	~ 10 years (variable across Europe)	10 years (indefinitely renewable)	Author's lifetime + 70 years
Where to seek protection through registration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National patent office • European Patent Office (EPO) • World IP Organisation (WIPO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National patent offices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National TM offices • OHIM • (EU TM & Design Registry) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Automatic • No registration required • Protection societies can be joined

4.2 Suggestions for protecting the RECIRCULATE project IPRs

The following suggestions¹ are made for protecting the IPRs developed during the RECIRCULATE project. These are based on those suggestions made during the IPR training that took place in January 2026. That training was based on the conclusions regarding the state of the art for each **KER** that was recorded in the report for the **2nd Iteration T-FA**. The current suggestions are based on the more recent conclusions regarding the state of the art for each **KER** that are recorded in **Section 3.2** of this report on the **3rd Iteration T-FA**, above.

KER1 – Assessment protocols and equipment for SOC, SOH, and SOS for packs, modules and cells

Suggestion – This is a highly saturated patent landscape and it is suggested that beneficiaries should consider protecting the protocols and equipment developed in the RECIRCULATE project for this purpose as secret know-how rather than through patenting them². Associated databases and software will attract automatic protection but could also be maintained as secret know-how.

¹ Please note that these are suggestions only and **NOT** recommendations – see Disclaimer at ANNEX 2 of this report for more information on the limit of liability applicable to **EUREXPLOIT LTD** in preparing this report on the **3rd Iteration T-FA** on behalf of RECIRCULATE partner **ILL**.

² This does not preclude seeking patent protection; indeed, it is understood that **EURECAT** have already gone ahead with a patent application in this technology area, **EP25383553.2**, which is currently under evaluation.

KER2 – Validated AI-backed control process for automated pack to module and module to cell dismantling of an automotive EV, e-bike and stationary battery

Suggestion – Given the low number of relevant patent applications found to be published, this appears to be an area in which the beneficiaries could protect their inventions by patent. The AI algorithms and training databases will attract automatic protection but could also be maintained as secret know-how.

KER3 – BMS for monitoring and control of batteries in second-life applications from reuse and remanufacture

Suggestion – This also appears to be an area in which the beneficiaries might seek to protect their hardware inventions by patent. Any embedded firmware and monitoring and control software will attract automatic protection but could also be maintained as secret know-how.

KER4 – Process definition for faster and more accurate sorting by SoX and battery provenance (including the cathode and anode materials) for recycling

Suggestion – Again this seems to be an area in which the beneficiaries might seek to protect their hardware inventions by patent. Any embedded firmware and monitoring and control software will attract automatic protection but could also be maintained as secret know-how.

KER5 – Smart/safe shipping/storage solution for second-life batteries

Suggestion – The area of smart transportation is likely to be heavily patented in related technology areas, e.g. for refrigerated transportation, so any RECIRCULATE inventions might appear obvious to *‘the ordinary person skilled in the art’*. Protection as secret know-how is an option in this circumstance.

KER6 – Blockchain-backed marketplace prototype (TRL8) for trusted trading of batteries and related components for reuse, remanufacture or recycling

Suggestion – Given the potential lack of Novelty or Inventive Step, protection as secret know-how might be preferred over patenting for RECIRCULATE advances in this technology area.

4.3 Overall summary of suggested RECIRCULATE IPR protection strategies

The above suggestions regarding protection of the RECIRCULATE IPRs are summarised in the following table taken from the January IP Training session:

*	Patent	Secret know-how**	Database ©/Database Right	Software ©/Software Right
KER1	+	++++	++	++
KER2	+++	+++	++	++
KER3	+++	+++	++	++
KER4	+++	+++	+++	++
KER5	++	+++	+	+
KER6	-	+	+++	+++
KEY	- not suggested as means of protection + to ++++ from least to most highly suggested			

*Note that registering trademarks for any product or process invented during the RECIRCULATE project is also an option

**Note that secret know-how is only as good as the CDAs/NDAs it is based on and the firm policing thereof

5. Summary of the current SotA vs Freedom to Operate [FTO]

5.1 Patentability of the RECIRCULATE project results

The three main criteria for an invention to attract patent protection are that it must be **novel over the prior art**, it must be **capable of industrial applicability**, and, most importantly, it must **involve an inventive step**, that is, the inventor must have made an unprecedented leap of imagination to create it that is non-obvious to ‘the ordinary person skilled in the art’ in their particular technology sector or in related sectors. The examiner of any patent application will look to its Claims to see if these three criteria are met. Then, so long as it is not excluded from patentability by legislation in the local jurisdiction, it may be granted a patent.

When the partners in the RECIRCULATE project contemplate making patent applications for any of their inventions in the project, they must ensure that those inventions meet the three criteria listed above before doing so. This will require them (or their patent attorneys) to undertake a patentability search, that is, to search the patent databases for prior art that might prevent them from getting a patent. The prior art can be found in, *inter alia*, scientific publications, in blogs on the internet, in patent applications that were not or might not be granted and in granted patents. Should they find that their invention meets the three criteria, they may then choose to submit a patent application for it.

5.2 FTO with the RECIRCULATE project results

Should they be lucky enough to be eventually awarded a patent for their invention(s), the partners should then have freedom to operate [FTO] with it (them) on markets in that jurisdiction and in any other where a patent is granted³.

As far as FTO with the actual RECIRCULATE project results is concerned this cannot yet be judged as it appears that many of the processes/products are to be completed very close to the end of the project or shortly thereafter and their potential for patentability and/or infringing third party IPRs cannot therefore be properly assessed.

What can be said is that only a few relevant patents or patent applications were found during the searches for this **3rd Iteration T-FA** and so the partners may well be able to get patent protection for their inventions and eventually enjoy FTO with them (see ‘suggestion’ for protecting the RECIRCULATE IPRs at **Section 4** above). However, each patent search provides only a snap-shot of the SotA on the day on which it was undertaken. Therefore, it will be essential for the partners to continue to monitor competitor patenting and commercial activity, using the likes of **Google Alerts**, throughout the remainder of the RECIRCULATE project and beyond (see **Section 6** that follows for details of how this may be achieved).

³ Note that there may be reasons why they do not have FTO with their granted patent, for example, it might be challenged in the courts by a competitor and subsequently revoked.

6. Monitoring technology developments in battery recycling

6.1 Setting of RECIRCULATE battery recycling alerts

To monitor developments in the RECIRCULATE technology arena, alerts can be set up with, for example,

 using the same key words and phrases used in the patent searches above:

The screenshot shows a Google Alert interface for the search term "Electric vehicle battery recycling". The alert is set up to send notifications to an email address (indicated by the "Enter email" field). Below the alert settings, a list of search results is displayed, each with a title, source, and a brief description.

Search Term: Electric vehicle battery recycling

Alert Settings: Enter email, Create Alert, Show options

Search Results:

- Commentary: Making EVs more eco-friendly - Recycling Today**
 Recycling Today
 The lifecycle of **EV batteries** presents environmental considerations that will require research and development for improvement.
- Innovative system for recycling lithium-ion batteries - All-About-Industries**
 All-About-Industries
 When an **electric vehicle** has reached the end of its life, it must be disposed of properly. This is not a problem when it comes to the bodywork, ...
- Circular discusses digital battery passports - Power Progress**
 Power Progress
 Volvo Cars to launch first commercially available **EV battery** passport The introduction comes well ahead of the 2027 deadline imposed by EU regulations ...
- SWITCH Mobility Taps Into EV Market With Extended Test Drives**
 Mobility Outlook
 Concerns around EVs often revolve around longer charging times, **battery** degradation, and the challenges of **battery recycling** and **disposal**. Addressing ...
- Northvolt factory in Canada could be delayed until 2028 - electrive.com**
 Electrive
 With the prospect of billions in subsidies and a growing **electric car** sales market, companies such as Northvolt and the VW **battery** subsidiary PowerCo ...

7. Conclusions

The conclusions from this part of **Deliverable D5.5** are clearly laid out in **Section 3** through **Section 5** above and summarised there and in the **Executive Summary**:

In summary, this **3rd Iteration T-FA** report has provided a timely update of the SotA in technology sectors relevant to the six anticipated **Key Exploitable Results [KERs]** of the project, whilst simultaneously providing an indication of the patentability of the projects results and the partners' freedom to operate [FTO] with those results now and in future.

ANNEX 1: Patent **Status** and utility models explained

A1.1 Patent **Status**

When patent applications are published, the examiner provides a report that goes along with the publication. The report usually comments on the Novelty of the invention(s) disclosed, whether or not they required an Inventive Step for their realisation and whether or not they are capable of Industrial Applicability.

Failure to meet any of the three criteria results in the application being rejected. This can then be followed by one or more re-applications, usually with amended claims.

Eventually, an application is:

- ✓ published as a granted patent;
- ✓ abandoned by the applicants in any jurisdiction where no further re-applications are permitted; or
- ✓ revised and resubmitted as a new application in the same or other jurisdiction.

When a PCT patent application is made through the agency of the World Intellectual Property Office [WIPO], the examiner first publishes what is called a ‘Written Opinion of the International Search Authority’ like this one taken from **RECIRC3-05** of this **3rd Iteration T-FA** report:

Status

Written Opinion of the International Search Authority*

Novelty: Claims 1-9: YES

Inventive Step: Claims 1-9: YES

Industrial Applicability: Claims 1-9: YES

Later, the same information is published as the ‘**International Preliminary Report on Patentability**’.

WIPO does not grant patents! Instead, it acts as a clearing house for simultaneous launch of patent applications across multiple global jurisdictions, e.g. the UK, China, Japan, the USA, Europe, Canada, Australia, etc., etc., where the applications are examined by the competent authorities in those jurisdictions. They decide the fate of that application in their jurisdiction. When that fate has not yet been determined, the WOISA or the IPRP – whichever is more recent, is included in **T-FA** reports so that readers can gain some insight into the likely fate of the application.

In the case of very recent applications to some patent offices, there may be no data available on the current fate of the application for some months after its publication. Where this was discovered in the patent searches for this report, the application is simply marked as ‘**Under examination**’ or ‘**Still under examination**’.

A1.2 Utility models

These are minor patents that can be awarded in some countries for inventions that are technical in nature but would not normally attract full patent protection.

They are often awarded for a shorter period than a full patent in the same jurisdiction. For example, a utility model in China will attract ten years protection rather than the full 20 years a granted Chinese patent would attract.

ANNEX 2: Disclaimer

EUREXPLOIT LTD endeavour to ensure the accuracy and completeness of our searches. However, because of possible human error, any publication delays, the availability and accuracy of machine translations, the subjective nature of such searches and possible incomplete data supplied to us, we cannot guarantee that our search reports are correct, complete or up to date. Our search reports are for informational purposes only.

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